

5th International Congress Advances in the Packaging Industry "Sustainability: Products and Processes"

PROCEEDINGS

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Following the success of previous editions, the **5th International Congress on “Advances in the Packaging Industry”** will take place on **March 27th and 28th, 2025**, in Milan, Italy. The event represents an important opportunity to bring together experts from academia and industry, offering a unique platform to discuss the latest innovations and future challenges in the packaging sector.

The congress will focus on technological advancements in the field of packaging, with special attention to packaging for food, pharmaceuticals, chemicals, and other industrial applications. Over the course of the two-day event, key topics for the future of the industry will be addressed, including innovative solutions for end-of-life materials, the use of bio-based and biodegradable materials, the integration of smart technologies into packaging systems, and the adoption of sustainable innovations in production processes such as lamination, printing, and surface treatments.

The congress will also serve as a reference point for analyzing strategies aimed at promoting the circular economy through eco-design and tools for the achievement of Life Cycle Assessment. There will also be a strong focus on regulatory and legislative aspects, which are crucial for driving technological innovations in compliance with safety and sustainability standards. Additionally, the potential of advanced materials for food preservation and waste valorization will be examined.

A significant highlight of this edition will be the organization of a roundtable discussion, featuring distinguished experts from all segments of the packaging supply chain. This moment of dialogue will offer a unique perspective on how the industrial world is adapting to address the sector’s challenges, with a particular emphasis on innovation, sustainability, and competitiveness. The roundtable will also serve as an opportunity to identify the strategies needed to support the evolution of the packaging industry in line with growing environmental and regulatory demands.

Milan, which has previously hosted a successful edition of the congress, returns as the center of this international event, providing a dynamic setting to foster dialogue and networking among the sector’s key players. The sessions, designed to cover both product-related and process-oriented aspects, will allow for in-depth exploration of technological innovations and practical applications.

The participation of distinguished speakers from around the globe will make this congress an unmissable event for those who wish to stay updated on new trends and help shape the future of sustainable packaging. Beyond discussing technological innovations, the congress will offer a unique opportunity to forge strategic collaborations and synergies between research and industry.

FOREWORD OF THE PROCEEDING EDITORS

It is our pleasure to present the proceedings of the 5th International Congress on Advances in the Packaging Industry. Sustainability: Products and Processes (API)

We are happy to compile proceedings consisting of 61 high-quality abstracts that demonstrate the continuous advancements in the scientific knowledge in the field.

All articles in this volume have been subjected to a peer-review process administered by the Proceeding Editors. We are thankful to all the referees who guaranteed the professional and scientific standards expected of API.

We strongly believe that Milan will inspire stimulating and high-quality scientific exchange between participants.

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RELIABILITY OF MONO-PE PACKAGING FOR CHEMICALS: a combined mixture design study

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Introduction

In industrial practice to meet requirements necessary for the reuse and recycling of materials, the use of monomaterial components is increasingly common. An exemplary case is certainly the packaging industry, where evolution is continuous on the development of new materials or new solutions to improve environmental impact given large production volumes. In this context, the present study seeks to analyse an industrial case related to improving the packaging of liquid household chemical products such as soaps and detergents through the use of a Polyethylene (PE) closure cap instead of Polypropylene (PP).

Materials and Methods

The materials considered are PE pouches that are industrially sealed by thermoforming and whose closure cap is inserted once the pouch is filled. In order to verify the reliability of the sealing of the PE closure cap in terms of number of failure, different possible variables were considered with the purpose of placing the component under stress conditions: type of commercial PE due to different stabilizer content (0-10 wt%), caps having different geometry (2 types), and different chemicals in contact with the pouch (6 types).

Given the large number of factor combinations to analyse, experimental and statistical data analysis was conducted by Design of Experiments approach with the purpose of limiting the experimental tests to be performed. For this, a Combined Mixture Design experimental design was set up in which the stabilizers were considered as mixture components, while the other parameters as factorial. The data analysis was performed through the multivariate analysis of the variance.

Results

In the first part of the study, the stability of the production materials was verified by analysing on different batches the structural (through Infra-Red spectroscopy) and thermal (through differential scanning calorimetry) properties. Subsequently, the results of the statistical analysis suggested that the interaction between PE and different chemical compounds that can be placed in the pouch is significant (p -value < 0.001) while the other factors considered such as the geometry of the cap or the presence of different stabilizers in the mixture does not produce any significant effect (p -value > 0.001) and therefore are not variables that contribute to the proper sealing of the pouch.

Conclusion

In this study has been assessed that the chemical employed as filler of the pouch plays a key role in determining the closure capacity of the PE cap, but the mono-PE solution is a viable solution from and industrial point of view in order to increase the environmental sustainability of the complete pouch.

As further development of this study a more deep investigation is needed in order to identify exactly the chemical reaction that is involved in the detriment of the PE, and that should be avoided to preserve the sealing effect of the caps of the pouch.

PARTIAL DEGRADABILITY OF CELLULOSE ACETATE IN COMPOSTING: consequences in terms of Life Cycle Assessment

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Cellulose acetate (CA) is a bioplastic that, depending on several factor such as the degree of substitution, can be compostable (as EN 13432 standard requires) or only biodegradable. According to Italian legislation, if the bioplastic is compostable, it can be delivered together with the Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste (OFMSW). However, if the waste treatment plants do not follow processes suitable to fully compost compostable bioplastics, even bioplastics certified as compostable could affect the final quality of the compost, making it “out-of-specification” (agriculture application not possible). In this context, this study aimed to demonstrate how an out-of-specification compost produces strongly negative implications in terms of environmental impacts.

For this scope, two methodological phases were considered. The lab phase (i) was aimed at obtaining compost from a sample of CA and Synthetic Food Waste (SFW), simulating the industrial treatment of CA together with the OFMSW. The experimental data were then used as data input for the LCA analysis (ii). CA was characterised by a degree of substitution of 2.45, a melting temperature in the range 230-250 °C, specific gravity of 1.31 and glycerol triacetate (CAS number 102-76-1) content of 30%. The CA sample in film was prepared according to the procedure reported in Gadaleta et al. (2022) and cut into squares of 25 × 25 mm; then, it was mixed with the SFW (average size of 10 mm) with a content of 2% (dry base). The biological treatment includes anaerobic digestion (AD) and composting (C). For AD, the process parameters were: HRT (hydraulic retention time) = 21 days, Temperature = 38°C, wet environment; for industrial composting: HRT = 90 days, Temperature = 58°C (active phase) and 38-25°C (curing phase). On the final compost, the plastic disintegration index, the phytotoxicity test (germination test) as well as the chemical-physical characterization was carried out. The process parameters of AD and C were also monitored during the tests. For the LCA study, 3 treatment scenarios were considered: CA with organic waste (S1), CA and plastic waste (S2) and CA and mixed waste (S3). The functional unit was 1 tonne of MSW. LCA modelling was performed using SimaPro 9 software with the Ecoinvent v3 database. Results showed how combined AD and C ensured significant disintegration of CA (73.8±24%). A wet anaerobic environment resulted in a better CA disintegration than the aerobic environment of composting. The 2% CA on the SFW did not influence the AD and C processes. However, the final compost was affected by the presence of undegraded bioplastics. As a consequence of this “out-of-specification” compost, LCA-results showed that the presence of CA in the organic waste stream (S1) had a negative effect on environmental performance. The impacts on global warming and stratospheric ozone depletion were respectively about 160% and 80% higher than in the other comparison scenarios (S2, S3). The results showed that in the presence of an out-of-specification compost, directly related to the non-compostability or partial degradability of bioplastics, the impacts on the environment are greater than those associated with the scenario of disposing of bioplastics together with mixed waste. In this case, it is crucial to adopt bioplastics that have fulfilled the compostability standard as well as ensure that more sustainable compostable materials could be available on the market.

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STUDY ON RECYCLABILITY OF POLYETHYLENE-POLYAMIDE FILMS

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Abstract

Plastic packaging nowadays is on the spotlight due to sustainability concerns. These concerns are related to the volume of waste generated and the consume of non-renewable feedstock, which can be addressed by recycling plastic packaging. In this direction goes upcoming European regulation that will be approved soon. A key factor on the recyclability of plastic packaging is composition: polymers, inks, adhesives, etc. Nowadays there is no clear criteria on the recyclability of packaging and different organizations with their own criteria have emerged. In this context there are doubts on the recyclability of some materials due to the lack of a harmonized criteria and clear information. One of the materials under discussion is polyamide, which is used in packaging due to its good mechanical properties and oxygen barrier. In this article the recyclability of a food packaging film containing polyethylene and polyamide will be studied using three different recyclability protocols and at the same time the protocols will be compared. These protocols not only analyse the recycling process but also take into consideration the properties of the final material by testing the recycled material on the application where the material originally is coming from: plastic films.

After all the tests it is determined that a market representative film with copolyamide 6/6.6 is recyclable, confirmed by all three protocols, and the presence of polyamide increased performance of some properties of the final recycled material.

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MEASURABLE SUSTAINABILITY: LCA GUIDELINES FOR FLEXIBLE PACKAGING ECO-DESIGN

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The environmental impact of flexible packaging has been extensively studied in the last years, both from flexible packaging manufacturing Companies and from their Associations; most of the studies focused their attention on LCA analysis based on available data bases, that are not specific for flexible packaging, bringing to results that are often not comparable.

The aim of the Giflex Scientific Committees is to draw up LCA guidelines for the eco-design of flexible packaging, the Giflex working protocol for the scientific-based assessment of the environmental impact of flexible packaging through Life Cycle Assessment studies, while building a culture of supply chains for the circularity of flexible packaging.

In line with the UNI EN ISO 14040:2021 and UNI EN ISO 14044:2021 standards, the working group compared, through an initial LCA methodology approach, the environmental impact of a flexible multi-material laminate (PET12mm-PE70mm) with a totally polyolefin-based one (OPP20mm-PE70mm), designed for recyclability and progressively lightened (OPP20 mm-PE60mm and OPP20mm-PE50mm) based on eco-design approach and opening up potential circularity scenarios for chemical recycling.

Several indicators and their quantification led to a comparative evaluation, in general, in favour of the OPP-PE structure with less PE thickness, with lower impacts than those with greater thickness of PE. The different LCA programs available lend themselves to the objectification of environmental impacts related to products, processes characteristic of the sector. Appropriate some alignment on the processes and peculiarities of the characteristic phases of transformation, cylinders, printing, lamination, cutting, preparation of logistics units typical of the sector.

LCA is an excellent tool for dealing with eco-design choices A balance must be struck between safety, intended as food protection aimed at ensuring an extension of shelf-life, and sustainability, understood as minimization of environmental impacts related to the life cycle of packaging starting from from the choice of raw materials to reuse, recycling, enhancement.

It is essential to develop a collection of data from the sector from the Giflex member members and their respective suppliers. It is one of the aims of a fundamental Alignment step for the sector and improvement of this guideline.

ADVANCING FLEXIBLE PACKAGING RECYCLABILITY TESTING

Learnings from CEFLEX testing programme to Enhance Recyclability Testing Methodologies

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Abstract

The transition to a circular economy demands reliable and actionable guidance on designing flexible packaging for recyclability. In response, CEFLEX launched its Designing for a Circular Economy (D4ACE) guidelines in 2020, marking a significant step in addressing the challenges associated with sortability and mechanical recyclability of flexible packaging structures in polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and mixed polyolefin (PO) streams. Building on these foundations, Phase 2 of the D4ACE programme has generated data to update design guidance for flexible packaging and, through the extensive sample testing, provided additional insights that have enabled the refinement of test methodologies to enhance the robustness and applicability of recyclability assessments.

This abstract presents key learnings from the CEFLEX Phase 2 recyclability testing programme, conducted between September 2022 and September 2024, in collaboration with academic institutions and technical experts. The programme included extensive testing of flexible plastic packaging materials and components in PE and PP mechanical recyclability, as well as further comparative analysis on control materials¹. This provided additional insights into the reliability and reproducibility of the test results, enabling further refinement of the testing methodologies². Observations reveal that while the testing framework effectively produces credible and independent data, targeted improvements in methodology are necessary to optimise clarity and reliability for future updates to design guidance, these learnings could be taken into other methodologies for recyclability certification testing.

Highlights include the validation of Engineered Base Materials (EBM) as a viable control standard, comparable to commonly used virgin resins, and insights into the impact of factors such as melt flow rate (MFR) variations on test outcomes. These findings underscore the importance of continuous refinement in recyclability testing to meet the evolving demands of circular packaging design.

This oral presentation will offer an in-depth exploration of lessons learned, focusing on practical recommendations for advancing testing protocols and thus enhancing the design-for-recycling guidelines that underpin the circular economy for flexible packaging.

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CIRCULAR ECONOMY EXPERT IN SUSTAINABLE PLASTIC PRODUCT: THE CIRCJET PROJECT

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CIRCJET is a 36-month-long European Erasmus+ project, which has developed a comprehensive, free, multilingual and tailor-made training course in Circular Economy (CE) on plastic materials at European level for both workers (i.e., C-VET, continuing vocational education and training) and students at secondary (i.e., I-VET – VET, initial vocational education and training VET) and university (i.e., I-VET-HE, initial vocational education and training higher education) levels. It involves twelve partners, among universities, clusters, VET and research centres, from six different European countries, namely Spain, Italy, Portugal, Germany, France and Lithuania.

The training course has been designed according to the needs and challenges faced by companies in the plastics sector and organized in eight training modules, each dealing with a different topic: Systemic Strategies on CE, Eco-design and LCA, Digital skills, Recycling with a focus on upcycling and downcycling approaches, Recovery, Manufacturing technologies for recycled materials and biomaterials, Users and usages and Entrepreneurship.

The main aim of this course and, more in general, of CIRCJET project, is to significantly enhance the skills and knowledge of professionals in the plastics industry, contributing to its innovation, resilience, and competitiveness, training individuals with the needed green skills and creating, therefore, the figure of a “Circular economy expert in sustainable plastic product”.

Piloting workshops with both companies and students were organized in each partners’ country during the last year (2024) to test and assess the developed contents, which are free, open and available on the project e-learning platform. Since the beginning of 2025, a validation phase of the complete and defined contents has been starting, again in each partner’s country.

This presentation is focused on the learning design strategies for the course creation, adopted by the partners and the educational tools available for the applicants are presented. The preparation and tools of the Recycling module, with a specific focus on plastic packaging sector, is presented as an example of the global structure of the course.

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IMPROVEMENT IN SOLVENT RECOVERY TECHNOLOGY FOR SOLVENT BASED PRINTING, LAMINATING AND CONVERTING PROCESSES

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Solvent recovery is a common practice for reducing the environmental impact of solvent based printing, laminating and converting processes.

It is mainly applied to rotogravure printing and lamination activities, but it can also be extended to flexographic printing and converting processes.

The technology allows both to reduce VOC (Volatile Organic Compounds) emissions to the atmosphere complying with the emission limits demanded by environmental regulations, and to reuse the solvent needed for diluting inks, adhesive and lacquers.

Solvent (VOC) is released into the atmosphere during the drying process of the films after the printing/laminating/converting activity. Solvent recovery is obtained filtering solvent vapours into multiple activated carbon beds, which are successively cleaned by a hot fluid. Solvent vapours are then condensed obtaining a liquid solvent blend.

The blend is then processed by a dehydration and distillation unit which allows to remove any excess of humidity and to separate different solvents with a purity degree able to consent their reuse in the production activity for diluting purposes.

Most recent European Community environmental regulations lead to a reduction of VOC emissions into the atmosphere and solvent recovery technology must be improved to respect those lower emissions limits.

Solvent recovery is also a high energy demanding process and currently ecological and social awareness is leading printing, laminating and converting players to proceed with an important further step towards sustainability, reducing energy consumption and carbon footprint.

Solvent recovery technology has now been improved and the most updated and efficient state of the art process is able not only to respect the most restrictive VOC emission limits, but also to significantly reduce thermal energy consumption, operating independently from fossil fuels and natural gas usage or considering renewable energy sources.

Improvement has been made developing modular solutions, introducing energy recovery steps in most of the sections of the plant, designing fully electrical heating systems, and introducing a final patented technology able to increase removal efficiency.

Specific technical solutions have also been patented for retrofitting existing solvent recovery plants, allowing printing, laminating and converting industries to comply with the newest environmental regulations.

IMPROVING Bioplastics Biodegradation in Composting

BIOFAST: Strategies to accelerate the biodegradation of bioplastics in industrial composting

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Biodegradable plastics represent a sustainable alternative for several products made of conventional polymers. Due to their capacity for degrading under controlled conditions, these materials offer an alternative end-of-life scenario such as industrial composting [1]. However, one of the main challenges for the adoption of biodegradable plastics lies in the lengthy testing required to validate their biodegradability and compostability. Current standard protocols such as those defined by EN 13432 [2], demand months of analysis to assess the behavior of materials under specific composting conditions. Accelerating biodegradation testing without compromising its reliability is, therefore, crucial to support the development and dissemination of more sustainable plastic solutions.

In this sense, the BIOFAST project aims to evaluate the effect of physio-chemical and biotechnological strategies and their combination for the acceleration of the biodegradation of compostable plastics at an industrial composting environment. The present abstract resumes the results obtained from the BIOFAST project, whose main work packages were: (i) enriching compost with agro-industrial by-products to promote accelerated biodegradation; (ii) evaluating physical degradation techniques for bioplastics to enhance biodegradation; and (iii) developing a new combined methodology to accelerate biodegradation under composting conditions.

Three types of compostable plastics were considered as samples: in 120 days, they reached a biodegradation degree ranging from 47 % to 69 %. When physical pretreatments (such as corona, plasma or ultraviolet irradiation, hydrothermal degradation with ultrasound, etc.) were applied, the overall level of biodegradation did not vary significantly. On the other hand the degree of biodegradation increased up to 70 % more than the standard method when using an enriched medium (mixing the compost with yeast, coffee powder and specific microorganisms active in the bioplastic biodegradation process). The coupled strategy (enriched medium and pretreatment) showed similar results than the approach based on the enriched medium alone, confirming the slight effect of pretreatments on the biodegradation process. Finally, ecotoxicity tests showed that the enriched medium did not have a toxic effect on the germination index and biomass yield of *Lolium perenne* and *Pisum sativum* species.

These results identify cost-effective and rapid techniques that could be used by companies to introduce new materials to the market, speeding up the testing phase. In addition, from a waste perspective, the present results can be upscaled at an industrial level to improve the treatment of these materials at full-scale plants.

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FUNCTIONAL UPCYCLING OF POST-CONSUMER PLASTIC FILMS

Transforming Waste into High-Value Secondary Raw Materials

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To meet the ambitious European recycling targets for 2030, it is essential to valorize even the most complex plastic waste streams, such as post-consumer flexible packaging. This research focuses on Fil-s, a secondary raw material obtained from the mechanical recycling of small-sized post-consumer plastic films. Fil-s is primarily composed of polyethylene (LLDPE and LDPE) with a minor polypropylene content (5-15% by weight, depending on the sorting plant).

The study explores upgrading strategies for Fil-s using the "*Design from Recycling*" approach, which aims to make recycled polymers suitable for specific applications by leveraging their intrinsic properties or through functional upcycling strategies. The goal is to maximize the added value of the recycled material, while minimizing costs and environmental impact [1]. Given its polyethylene composition, Fil-s shows favorable extensional rheological properties, making it a potential candidate for use as films, pipes, and foams.

Fil-s in its pristine form faced challenges with bubble stability during blown film extrusion, however, the addition of a maleic anhydride (MAH)-grafted compatibilizer and nanofillers improved both bubble stability and the uniform deformation of the film [2].

In the case of piping applications, the effects of washing treatments (at cold and hot conditions) and the addition of a MAH-grafted compatibilizer on the chemical-physical properties of Fil-s were first assessed. The recycled systems were then extruded as pipes by using a pilot scale plant, with the process resulting more stable and continuous with the compatibilized Fil-s, as it was deducible from its flow properties [3].

Finally, even if the shear and elongational rheological properties of Fil-s proved suitable for foam extrusion, its foamability was inferior to virgin LDPE due to incompatibility among its polyolefin fractions. Compatibilization through reactive extrusion with maleic anhydride resulted in more consistent density reductions (37%) compared to untreated Fil-s. Moreover, compatibilized Fil-s foams displayed more uniform morphology, higher stiffness, and greater tensile strength while maintaining similar ductility compared to the untreated material.

This research highlights how innovative upgrading strategies can transform a challenging recycled material like Fil-s into viable solutions for films, pipes, and foams, contributing to sustainable recycling and circular economy goals.

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EVALUATION OF POST-INDUSTRIAL POLYETHYLENE TEREPHTHALATE RECYCLATES (RPET) OBTAINED FROM MULTILAYER POLYETHYLENE TEREPHTHALATE (PET)/ POLYETHYLENE (PE) SHEETS

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Abstract

Trays made from thermoformed plastic sheets are the second major application of PET packaging after beverage bottles. Recycling of PET is highly encouraged in the European Union wherein ambitious recycling targets and incorporation contents in packaging are already set. Most PET-based trays are laminated with other polymers, such as polyethylene (PE) which is used for heat sealing. This makes the wastes, including clean post-industrial wastes (PIW) resulting from sheet trimming, not easily compatible with conventional recycling because of the quality deterioration of the recyclates. Industrial guidelines set strategies to make multilayer tray packaging recyclable applying currently existing procedures for PET flakes washing. However, detailed studies on the recyclates and recycled products obtained through these strategies, are limited. In this work, delamination of PIW from PET/PE thermoformed sheets were performed following industrial guidelines to recover PET and used to produce PET sheets with 100% and 20% (m/m) rPET content. The safety as food contact material and the quality (optical, rheological and thermal properties) of the recyclates and sheets produced were analysed in comparison to 100% (m/m) vPET sheets. The process was able to remove more than 95% of PE in PET/PE flakes. Significant quality changes were observed in 100% rPET sheets, in particular colour and intrinsic viscosity. Regarding thermal properties, only cold crystallization temperature was affected. Results from analyses through FTIR and GC-MS were combined with statistics and used to discriminate samples with rPET. Sheet production decreased the concentration of volatile and semi-volatile migrants as expected. However, higher concentration of oligomers, particularly trimers were found in sheets as compared to flakes.

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OPTIMIZING HIGH-BARRIER PBS-BASED BLENDS FOR SUSTAINABLE FLEXIBLE PACKAGING: MORPHOLOGICAL, PROCESSING, AND FUNCTIONAL PERSPECTIVES

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The transition toward sustainable materials has generated significant interest in biodegradable polymers capable of meeting the high-barrier requirements for flexible packaging applications [1]. Polybutylene succinate (PBS), a biodegradable aliphatic polyester, is a promising base material due to its excellent processability, thermal stability, and mechanical properties. However, its inherently poor barrier performance limits its application in high-barrier packaging [2]. Conversely, polyvinyl alcohol (PVOH) and butenediol vinyl alcohol copolymer (BVOH) offer exceptional barrier properties against oxygen and water vapor. Despite this, these hydrophilic polymers face challenges such as limited processability, mechanical brittleness, and high sensitivity to moisture [3-4].

This study explores the melt blending of PBS with PVOH and BVOH as a cost-effective strategy to combine and optimize their complementary properties, addressing their individual limitations. The novelty of this work lies in the development of PBS/PVOH and PBS/BVOH blends specifically tailored for flexible packaging, a topic underexplored in the literature.

Biodegradable blown films were developed from PBS/PVOH and PBS/BVOH blends across a broad compositional range (20:80 to 80:20 wt%) and characterized using thermogravimetric analysis, mechanical testing, oxygen and water vapor permeability measurements, and other key techniques.

The findings demonstrated that both PVOH and BVOH significantly improve the barrier properties of PBS, reducing oxygen and water vapor permeability by up to 60% compared to pure PBS films. However, the processability and functional performance of the blends were found to depend strongly on the chemical nature of the secondary polymer, the number of polar functional groups, and the extent of interfacial interactions with the PBS matrix. Analytical models for immiscible or partially miscible blends were applied to correlate phase morphology with macroscopic properties, enabling the prediction of material behavior in specific packaging applications. This study highlights the potential of PBS/PVOH and PBS/BVOH blends as sustainable, high-barrier materials for flexible packaging, offering a promising alternative to conventional non-biodegradable solutions.

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EXPLORING OLIVE KERNEL POWDER AS A FILLER IN PBAT BIOCOMPOSITES FOR PACKAGING APPLICATIONS

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The increasing consumer awareness of sustainability is driving the materials industry toward alternative solutions. In the food packaging sector, where materials must ensure food safety and shelf-life extension, the challenge lies in developing eco-friendly alternatives to conventional plastics.

Biocomposites made from biodegradable matrices and agro-industrial waste fillers are emerging as a promising alternative in the food packaging industry [1]. These materials offer an eco-friendly solution to the environmental challenges posed by traditional plastics, aligning with the principles of sustainability and circular economy. Despite their potential, further research is crucial to address the trade-offs between functionality, performance, and safety when integrating natural fillers into polymer matrices. However, while such technologies hold significant potential to reduce the environmental footprint of packaging, they also raise critical concerns regarding consumer safety, such as chemical migration, premature degradation of the polymer matrix, and microbiological contamination [2].

This study explores the potential of PBAT-based biocomposites reinforced with olive kernel powder (OKP), a natural filler derived from olive industry by-products, for the development of sustainable food packaging materials. By incorporating OKP, the research promotes circular economy principles while improving the material's mechanical properties.

Biocomposites with varying OKP concentrations (10%, 15%, 20%, and 30%) were prepared and extensively characterized. Mechanical testing revealed that OKP improved the elastic modulus of the samples, while higher concentrations reduced elongation at break, highlighting the need to balance mechanical strength and flexibility. Rheological analysis indicated increased viscosity with higher OKP content, impacting processability but maintaining potential for film-blowing applications. Morphological analysis (SEM) revealed better filler dispersion at lower OKP levels, while overall matrix-filler adhesion appeared moderate. Thermal characterization (DSC) indicated slight changes in melting temperature and crystallinity, while wettability tests suggested reduced hydrophobicity, which could support enhanced environmental degradation.

This research highlights the potential of PBAT/OKP biocomposites as a sustainable alternative for food packaging applications, advancing both material performance and the use of agro-industrial waste within a circular economy framework.

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PLA-PET COPOLYMER FOR FOOD PACKAGING APPLICATION

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The aim of this work is to synthesize a copolymer based on poly lactic acid (PLA) and poly ethilen terephthalate (PET). This would allow the synthesis of a new and partially biodegradable material with improved properties compared to PLA alone. In food packaging, in general, the use of biopolymers is only suitable for a few types of food that do not require high barrier properties. No sustainable material that can replace petrochemical polymers with the standards of the latter still exists. This work shows the design of a biodegradable material for flexible packaging with improved barrier and mechanical properties compared to a biopolymer, where a nanocrystalline structure that preserves transparency could be still achieved. Existing studies on PLA-PET blends [1-3] demonstrated that it is possible to obtain a transesterification between low molecular weight PLA and PET, though a reactive mixing [4]. The reaction would be aided by a suitable temperature and the presence of a catalyst. A commercially available PET based polyol was selected as its chemical structure is a low molecular weight PET and it can be processed at the processing temperature of PLA. Several ratios PLA:PET were studied so that the resulting copolymer contained a high biodegradable fraction. The polymers were melt compounded in a nitrogen atmosphere and different mixing times were studied. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out to analyse the reaction products that were generated from the reactive mixing studying the degradation behaviour. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) were employed to study the degree of the reaction. In particular, a deconvolution analysis of the carbonyl peak showed some changes in the chemical structure. Analytical chemistry investigation (Gas Chromatography and Liquid Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry) validated the results of previous analysis. The results obtained show that the interaction between the two polymers is capable of generating different reaction products than the physical mixture, also encouraged by the presence of the catalyst.

SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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TANNINS AS BIO-BASED ADDITIVES FOR SMART FOOD PACKAGING

Developing PHAs-tannin films with multifunctional properties

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Similarly to other sectors in the plastics industry, the food packaging sector - where the lifetime of plastic products can be as short as a few days - is experiencing a rapid and deep revolution with the introduction of bio-based and biodegradable materials. The extensive use of fossil-based plastics with short shelf-life has pushed the research towards polymeric materials derived from biomass or valorising waste from other production processes^[1]. Besides this innovation, there are other significant developments in this field; currently, increasing attention has been given to developing the so-called “smart packaging”, where the material is able to enhance and monitor food shelf-life through active or intelligent features. In this work, an innovative bioplastic formulation was developed combining polyhydroxybutyrate-*co*-valerate (PHBV) with wood tannins as bio-based multifunctional additives. PHBV/tannin films with increasing tannin concentrations (0, 1, 5, and 10 phr) were obtained via solvent casting. Formic acid was chosen as an environmentally friendly alternative to chloroform, a conventional solvent for polyhydroxyalkanoates. The successful homogeneous incorporation of tannins resulted in flexible polymeric films with antioxidant activity, UV-blocking properties, and high barrier properties against oxygen and moisture. In particular, radical DPPH assay results revealed that films containing 5 and 10 phr of tannins achieved complete scavenging within 10–30 minutes, demonstrating outstanding antioxidant properties. Furthermore, all these samples exhibited excellent UV protection, attributed to the UV absorption properties of the aromatic rings in the tannins’ polyphenolic structure. Moreover, DSC analysis confirmed that all PHBV/tannin samples remained suitable for both refrigerated and ambient temperatures. Finally, exposure of the PHBV/tannin films to ammonia vapors resulted in an eye-visible color shift from yellow to dark brown, highlighting the material's potential as colorimetric indicator for food spoilage detection, such as monitoring fish degradation. These findings suggest that the incorporation of tannins positively affects the final material properties, offering a valuable strategy for developing sustainable alternatives to fossil-based plastics in advanced food packaging applications.

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BIODEGRADABLE PVA/STARCH FILMS WITH ZEOLITE ADDITIVE

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Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) is a synthetic biodegradable polymer widely applied in packaging due to its high mechanical and sealing performance. Blending PVA with starch enhances its biodegradability and water resistance while lowering production costs [1]. Additionally, zeolite additives have been reported to improve the mechanical, thermal, and barrier properties of biodegradable films, along with potential interest for ‘active’ packages [2]. Therefore, in this study, fine zeolite 13X powder was incorporated in opportunely prepared PVA/starch (P/S) aqueous formulations as a multifunctional additive; then, rod-coating and drying of the formulations were employed to obtain thin films. The preparation conditions were carefully optimised to obtain films with good final dispersion of zeolite additive, particularly as tested with FTIR-ATR spectroscopy. Among preliminary characterizations of films, water vapor permeability (WVP) tests were conducted. Besides testing films’ mechanical and thermal properties, it is planned to exchange zeolites with antimicrobial ions and also evaluate gas scavenging activity. Natural zeolite clinoptilolite will be taken into consideration as well.

Effect of zeolite incorporation on films' WVP

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PHBV-BASED MATERIALS FOR FOOD PACKAGING APPLICATIONS

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The transition of society to a more sustainable way of living is of crucial importance to guarantee the well-being of the next generations. In this context, biobased polymers have gained attention from both academia and industry in the last decades. They are proposed as a real sustainable alternative to fossil-based plastics. Within this family, poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV), is gaining ground in the field due to its magnificent properties and wide biodegradability profile.

Microorganisms use a wide variety of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorous sources for growth and PHBV accumulation. In order for PHBV production to compete with that of petroleum based polymers in the world today, the substrates must originate from a biomass source that is considered either of low value or from a waste stream, to make the process as economically attractive as possible [1]. Through 3 funded projects, selecting *Haloferax mediterranei* as microorganism, we had the opportunity to produce PHBV from different organic wastes: in upPE-T we tested: a) candy industry waste and b) *comamonas testosteroni* biomass obtained from the bioconversion of TPA coming from the enzymatic degradation of PET plastic waste; in the case of ViSS we started from poultry and candy industry wastes; in Agro2Circular we started from lemon and apple wastes.

Given the inherently high content of free sugars in these residues, it was not necessary to apply any form of pre-treatment or pre-fermentation process to increase the bioavailability of these naturally available “waste” sugars. Interestingly, all the conditions tested produced PHBV with high content in the comonomer 3-hydroxyvalerate (between 10 and 14 %; ten times higher than the commercial PHBV). The content in 3-hydroxyvalerate was easily increased (up to 30%) by the addition of precursors. Even if all the wastes have proved to be good sources for the effective growth of the *H. Mediterranei* biomass and production of PHBV, in terms of production yield the best organic waste was found to be lemon extract. The PHBV production process has been optimised and scale up to 300 L bioreactors, and the pristine PHBV produced formulated in blends and compounded to achieve the required properties to be processable by the conventional technologies (blown extrusion, injection moulding, and thermoforming) into rigid, semirigid and flexible packaging.

In upPE-T project, flexible films, semirigid trays and sticks have been realised. The PHBV based formulations have been then validated, involving four food sectors – dairy, bakery, meat and candies. Applying pre-existing process plant and procedures, simulation of the packaging process in real food production conditions (in-line), including test of weldability, has been done and prototypes of food packed products have been realised. Each end user contributed to comparing technical characteristics of the upPE-T packaging with conventional packaging materials (such as PE, PET, or PP) currently used. Shelf-life studies have been performed both from the sensorial and microbiological point of view, comparing the standard with the new biobased-biodegradable material. Results were promising in the case of lollipops, bakery and dairy sectors, while some issues still need to be solved for meat being the product more sensitive to water vapour and oxygen. PHBV-based material can represent a future alternative to fossil-based biopolymers in food packaging in sectors where barrier properties are not particularly restrictive.

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PROCESSING AND PROPERTY ASSESSMENT OF BIOBASED POLY(LACTIC ACID)/POLY(BUTYLENE SEBACATE) (PLA/PBSE) BINARY BLEND FILMS

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Abstract

To successfully introduce sustainable bioplastics into the packaging market, they must possess a processing window wide enough to support shaping operations such as film production, along with a structure that ensures adequate technological performance [1]. Some polymers are more promising than others; for instance, Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) has reached a level of technological maturity and production scalability. Conversely, other bioplastics, such as Poly(butylene sebacate) (PBSe), synthesized using bio-derived 1,4-butanediol and sebacic acid obtained from castor oil, are emerging with unique properties that make them noteworthy candidates for further exploration and development [2]. Indeed, the blending of polymers is a well-established strategy in materials science and polymer engineering, enabling the creation of materials with tailored properties and enhanced performance compared to individual polymers [3]. Specifically, this study focuses on the development and comprehensive characterization of novel biobased and biodegradable recipes blending PLA and PBSe in order to obtain micrometric films. These blends were particularly tailored for applications in packaging, aiming to leverage the complementary properties of PLA and PBSe. The work carried out involved twin-screw extrusion, preceded by a Design of Experiments (DoE) aimed at optimizing the process parameters. The melt strength was measured in-line on these granules, along with the melt flow, to identify the optimal viscosity/temperature correlation for producing filmable materials. Subsequently, the films obtained were characterized in terms of thermomechanical properties, sealability, barrier properties, and fracture behavior. These results were correlated with the morphology and microstructures generated during both primary and secondary processing.

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INSECT PROTEIN-BASED BIOPLASTICS

Black Soldier Fly as sustainable source of raw materials

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The increasing global demand for sustainable biomaterials is often hindered by issues related to resource competition with food crops, high production costs, and limited functionality [1]. In this context, insect-derived proteins offer a highly novel and sustainable solution. Among these the bioconverter insect *Hermetia illucens*, commonly known as Black Soldier Fly (BSF), has the ability to easily transform any type of organic waste into high-sustainable insect biomass. BSF larvae biomass is particularly rich in proteins of high biological value, which have primarily gained attention as animal feed [2]. Furthermore, BSF proteins could be explored as raw material for bioplastics due to their film-forming properties. We investigated the realization of self-standing bioplastics films using BSF proteins through the wet casting technique. Protein extraction was performed on defatted BSF larvae powder using a modified method based on Caligiani *et al.* [3]. Various protocol conditions were examined to enhance protein solubilization and biofilm formulation. Among additives, we evaluated the impact of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) as surfactant and glycerol as plasticizer on film-forming properties through a chemical-physical characterization. BSF protein dissolved in water with 15 or 20% w/w glycerol (Gly) exhibited good film forming properties, though high pH values are necessary for optimal solubilization. The use of SDS reduced both the pH and the glycerol content, while achieving more homogeneous films with comparable tensile strength and strain (Fig.1). These results highlight the potential of BSF proteins as a sustainable and alternative raw material for the production of bioplastics. Further studies are needed to improve the sustainability of the processes, such as optimizations of the protein extraction and the use of more eco-friendly surfactants.

Fig.1: Tensile measurements and typical photograph of the BSF protein-based film

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DEVELOPMENT OF PBSA COMPOSITES WITH RED GRAPE SKINS POWDER

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This work investigated the potential of using a wine-making by-product as a natural and green filler in the production of biodegradable composites with poly(butylene succinate-*co*-adipate) (PBSA). The grape skins powder (GSP) samples were obtained from fermented red grape pomace of a mix of Sangiovese and Merlot varieties, sourced from a winery in Tuscany during a previous project. The pomace was dried at 60 °C, after which the skins were separated from stalks and seeds and then milled ($\leq 250 \mu\text{m}$). The GSP was characterized for its chemical composition and antioxidant properties. GSP revealed a notable protein content (11.18%), 7.54% ashes and 52.61% insoluble dietary fiber. Extractable phenolics were quantified as 22.91 mg GAE/g (gallic acid equivalents) with antioxidant capacity equivalent to 194.85 $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$ (Trolox equivalents).

The thermal stability of the filler was assessed by TGA in an oxidative atmosphere. Results showed that, after an initial slight loss ($< 5 \text{ wt}\%$) the filler remained stable up to 240 °C, which is well above the melting temperature of the matrix, enabling the compounding process. PBSA and the filler (GSP) were melt-mixed, after drying, in different proportion (0, 5, 10, 15, 20 wt%), using a Brabender mixer. The mixing time and rotational speed were kept constant for all the samples (4 min, 100 rpm), while the processing temperature was adjusted slightly (from 130 °C to 145 °C) on account of an increased viscosity at higher filler loadings. The filler addition caused only a slight and nearly constant decrease the melt flow rate of the matrix. Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC) indicated no remarkable changes in molecular weight across all composite samples, underlying no negative effects of the filler on the stability of PBSA. Moreover, thermal properties (analyzed by DSC and TGA) were not impacted by the incorporation of the filler.

Dog-bone specimens, conforming to ISO 527-2, were obtained by injection molding for mechanical testing. The results showed that the addition of the filler induced a fragile behavior, more pronounced at higher filler loadings. However, at lower concentrations, the sample retained their deformability. To improve filler dispersion and maintain deformability, the use of a plasticizer could be considered. Films $200 \pm 20 \mu\text{m}$ thick were obtained by compression molding to be tested for antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus* or *E. coli* (ISO 22196:2011 standard).

The films demonstrated high antimicrobial activity, with inhibition percentages exceeding 93% in all cases and reaching the 99.990% for *E. coli* and 99.529% for *S. aureus*. Migration tests were also conducted in accordance with Regulation (EU) No 10/2011. Specifically, food simulants A, B, and D2 were used under contact conditions of 10 days at 40°C to evaluate the overall migration.

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RHEOLOGICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND FILMABILITY OF A BIOCOMPOSITE MADE OF A BIODEGRADABLE POLYMER AND TOMATO BY-PRODUCTS FOR PACKAGING APPLICATION

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The increasing environmental concerns associated with conventional plastics have intensified the need for sustainable alternatives in the packaging industry. Biodegradable and compostable polymers, particularly those reinforced with natural fillers, represent a promising solution to reduce plastic waste and promote circular economy principles. Utilizing agro-industrial residues as fillers not only valorizes waste streams but also reduces reliance on virgin resources, making these materials highly attractive for eco-friendly applications, such as heavy-duty bags.

This study focused on the production of biodegradable and compostable films using natural fillers derived from by-products of tomato sauce production. The fillers were subjected to a multi-step preparation process: drying, coarse grinding using a kitchen mixer, and fine milling through ball milling process. A sieving process followed, isolating particles smaller than 45 µm. The polymer and filler were melt mixed in a internal mixer at 190 °C and subsequently extruded using a single-screw extruder with a temperature profile of 160-170-180-190°C. The extruded composite was pelletized and rheologically characterized in shear and elongational flow.

The biocomposite exhibited good processability and was successfully processed into homogeneous films as is possible to notice from Figure 1. Mechanical characterization confirmed that the resulting films possess good properties suitable for heavy-duty bag applications.

Figure 1. Film blowing process of biocomposite based on by-products of tomato sauce production.

These findings highlight the potential of incorporating tomato processing by-products into biodegradable polymer matrices to create sustainable packaging solutions. The developed biocomposite demonstrates a viable pathway for advancing circular bio-economy practices while addressing the growing demand for environmentally friendly materials.

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SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING: The Shift from Synthetic to Bio-Based Colorants

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Abstract

The global demand for sustainable packaging solutions has increased interest in developing natural-based and more environmentally friendly colorant systems. Colors in packaging are crucial for branding, consumer perception, and product communication, making their environmental impact, feasibility of use, and performance properties essential. This scientific paper explores the transition from synthetic to bio-based colorants, focusing on their potential, challenges, and implications for the packaging industry.

A significant part of this paper examines the feasibility of replacing synthetic pigments with natural bio-based colorants, particularly in the dyeing, coating, and printing of packaging materials. The comparison to solvent-based inks is also addressed, with a focus on transitioning to water-based alternatives. Water-based inks offer a safer option, though they come with challenges related to energy consumption during the drying process, which also has an influence on the overall carbon footprint.

Through a combination of empirical studies, literature review, and other information sources, this paper highlights the applications and potential of natural colorants in the packaging and printing sector. Various sources of bio-based colorants are explored, including industrial by-products, which hold promise as sustainable alternatives to synthetic pigments. The paper evaluates the availability, properties, and industrial-scale usability of these bio-based colorants, aiming to reduce the dependency on synthetic materials while addressing global industry needs.

Key findings indicate that transitioning to bio-based colorants is feasible within certain limits and conditions. However, challenges remain in achieving industrial-scale scalability, ensuring consistent quality, maintaining product performance, and affordable pricing. The paper emphasizes the potential of innovative colorant sources, such as industrial by-products, which could influence ecological footprints while meeting industry demands.

This paper is based on research conducted at Tampere University of Applied Sciences (TAMK) and also incorporates insights from a thesis work completed at TAMK. These studies underscore the complexities of balancing sustainability, product quality, and economic viability. They also highlight the need for continued innovation to overcome the challenges of adopting natural bio-based colorants on a global industrial scale.

In conclusion, the development of sustainable packaging color solutions is critical in reducing the environmental footprint of packaging. By addressing issues of scalability, usability, and carbon footprint reduction, this research provides actionable insights for advancing eco-friendly practices in the packaging industry while maintaining functionality and cost-effectiveness.

NON-VOLATILE COMPOUNDS IN PBAT FOOD PACKAGING MATERIAL

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The need for alternatives to conventional plastics has growing interest and research in the development of biodegradable materials, particularly for use in food packaging, where environmental impact and safety are key considerations.

In this study, the chemical safety of a polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT) biodegradable material was investigated using LC-HRMS, Q Exactive Orbitrap. Acetonitrile extract of the PBAT pellets and migration into food simulants (such as simulants of aqueous and fatty foods) were analyzed in positive and negative ionization modes. HRMS data were acquired in one-dimensional HRMS and MS/HRMS using data dependent acquisition (DDA) mode to identify fragmentation patterns. The objective was to tentatively identify potential migrating compounds that could affect food safety. In addition, the toxicity of the detected compounds was estimated using the Cramer decision tree, an *in silico* methodology based on molecular structures.

The results revealed the presence of several compounds directly related to the structure of PBAT, including linear and cyclic oligomers, which were tentatively identified by comparing mass spectral data with a theoretical in-house database. This database was developed from the expected starting materials used in the synthesis of PBAT, considering the expected ion adducts formed under experimental conditions. Oligomers have often been considered non-intentionally added substances (NIAS) [1], raising concern about their potential toxicity and migration into food.

This study highlights the applicability of HRMS for the comprehensive characterization of complex matrices, enabling the identification of unknown compounds and contributing to risk assessments. Furthermore, some of the tentatively identified oligomers were classified within Cramer class III, meaning potential high toxicity. This work underscores the importance of evaluating the chemical safety of innovative packaging materials, ensuring their compliance with food contact regulations while fostering the transition toward a circular economy.

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TOWARDS VALORIZATION AND SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING.

Active films enriched with cherry by-products

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Given the growing interest in sustainable alternatives, fruit by-products have gained attention as alternatives to petroleum-based food packaging materials since they are a rich source of compounds, such as pectins that could be used as biopolymers. Moreover, the presence of bioactive compounds, including polyphenols made them a sustainable option to develop active packaging [1]. The current study aimed to encapsulate cherry extract to develop active and edible films using an eco-friendly approach.

A cherry polyphenol-rich extract yielded from cherry by-products was employed to provide antioxidant activity in edible films. The basis of the formulation was composed of 1% w/v of pectin, 0.5% w/v of glycerol, and $\text{CaCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ at 0.02% w/v, added for reticulation purposes. The extract was incorporated by antisolvent precipitation employing zein protein as encapsulation material to reach a final concentration of 5, 10, and 20% w/w in films.

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) was used to determine the particle size, polydispersity index (PDI) and Z-potential of the formulations. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), image analysis through scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) were utilized to characterize the active films. Migration assays were conducted to evaluate the release of active compounds and their antioxidant properties following accelerated storage conditions, in compliance with Regulation (UE) n° 10/2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food. Phenolic compounds were confirmed using LC-MS/MS and quantified through HPLC-DAD.

Based on the Z-potential values, the incorporation of the extract-zein solution into the base formulation leads to an increase in its stability, with values of approximately -40 mV. The particle size range from 0,7 μm to 0,9 μm .

Migration assays have shown the release of active compounds from cherry-loaded films, regarding their higher antioxidant capacity, enhanced from ~40% to ~70% with the increasing extract concentration. Additionally, the principal phenolic compounds observed in the extract were released, such as neochlorogenic and chlorogenic acid, whose concentrations ranged from 30 to 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^2$ in both cases.

Cherry extract yielded from industrial by-products has demonstrated antioxidant activity after accelerated migration conditions. Antisolvent precipitation has proven to be a useful technique to encapsulate polyphenols to produce active packaging, reducing fruit industrial wastes under a circular economy framework.

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MOBILITY OF PFAS IN PACKAGING **from design to end-of-life**

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PFAS are known as persistent and mobile contaminants present also in packaging.

They could contaminate packaging both as intentionally and not intentionally added substances.

In the first case, they are added to food contact materials in particular for their anti-greasing and water-proof characteristics. PFAS can also be present unintentionally, due to production or to raw materials contaminations.

Packaging producers and latest regulations are trying to limit the presence of PFAS in packaging: ECHA initiatives, PPWR draft, but also self-regulation for compostable packaging set limits in the use of intentionally added PFAS.

Beyond the legislative requirements, packaging has different life stages that can be at risk of contamination. Packaging can be a source of PFAS during its use, triggering the risk of food contamination, and they can release PFAS during the end-of-life stages, thus polluting the environment.

Is there really a mobility of these contaminants, from the design phase to the end-of-life?

The experimental focus tries to answer this question, starting from compostable items.

If the plastic film is contaminated with PFAS, and it is disposed into home or industrial composting plant, will we find PFAS contamination also in final compost? And will the PFAS be absorbed by plants growing on it?

We checked for their concentration using the different techniques also mentioned in the final version of PPWR draft: targeted analysis, TOP Assay (looking for precursors) and total organic fluorine.

The test will be performed while conducting an ecotoxicity study according to EN 13432 in which a test matrix will be putted in contact with PFAS and will then be used for germination studies. The determination of PFAS concentration will be operated both on the test matrix, at different timepoints, and on the plants at the end of the ecotoxicity tests.

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OPTIMUM FORMULATION DESIGN OF PBS/GLOCHIDS BIOCOMPOSITES FOR AGRI-FOOD APPLICATIONS

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The aim of this work has been to design and produce biocomposites with enhanced performance, entirely made from renewable sources [1], that offer significant advantages in terms of eco-sustainability as they promote the development of circular economies, while ensuring the same technological functionality as traditional composites. As there is limited understanding about the balance of different physical properties in biocomposites, optimizing their properties is an important consideration for a more widespread application. In this study, the Design of Experiments (DOE) approach was used to statistically develop an optimum formulation for biocomposites based on PBS (polybutylene succinate) and natural fibers derived from agri-food waste [2]. In particular, the chosen fibers are the glochids (G) of *Opuntia ficus-indica* fruits, since their surface, covered by numerous everted barbs, may have the potential to promote interfacial adhesion with the polymeric matrix.

Biocomposites were prepared at different fiber concentrations using the melt compounding technique in a twin-screw extruder. Mechanical properties of the biocomposites were first experimentally measured. Then, the DOE approach was utilized to generate, once selected parameters are set, response models for different properties. In particular, as selected factors are chosen the weight concentration of PBS and glochids, while the objective was to maximize the Young's modulus and maintain the elongation at break at an acceptable value of around 18%.

The software used is JMP Pro 18 (JMP®, SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA), which suggested four test formulations for the biocomposites (0, 14, 20, and 30 wt%) and identified as the optimal the one loaded at 14 wt% of G. The validation procedure, through performing tensile mechanical and heat deflection temperature (HDT) analyses, confirmed the software outputs and demonstrated significant improvements in elastic modulus (+40%) and heat deflection temperature (HDT) (more than 10°C), without a significant reduction in ductility, for the optimal biocomposite formulation. The same approach was subsequently used to evaluate the impact of repeated mechanical recycling on systems' performance, simulating up to three reprocessing cycles. Again, the validation confirmed the DOE results that identified the optimal properties' preservation in system at 17 wt% G loading and recycled 3 times, so demonstrating that the DOE approach has a great potential in supporting the design of biocomposites with an optimal balance of compositional and performance requirements.

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PLASTIC BLENDS FROM POTATO BY-PRODUCTS

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Introduction

The growing amount of agricultural and food wastes is becoming a major concern, pushing to find new strategies for their processing and value-added reuse to enable a sustainable use of feedstock and reduce the environmental impact. By-products of potatoes, abundant in many countries, can be valorized by leading to economic and environmental benefits. Potato wastes (leaves, discarded potatoes, pulp and peels) were considered as source for the extraction, by green methodologies, of starch and lignin fractions which were used in the preparation of blends with polylactic acid (PLA) to produce films for ecosustainable food packaging.

Experimental

Potato starch, obtained by enzymatic synthesis, was thermoplasticized (TPPS) and then melt blended at different percentages (20, 25, and 30 %wt.) with two different grades of Ingeo Biopolymer (2003D and 4060D) PLA from NatureWorks. With a Xplore Microcompounder 5&15cc extruder, coupled with a Xplore Film Device BR65, the bioplastics were mixed and the cast films were produced in a single process. Lignin from potato plant was functionalized with four different methods and the 4 lignin-based additives (L, L-EC, L-EC-Lac, L-PS) were used in the best TPPS/PLA blend to produce films with modified characteristic properties, such as antioxidant activity, contact angle and oxygen permeability.

Results

Upon visual observation, PLA/TPPS films maintain clarity and good transparency although lignin additives give slight brown tones. The film samples 30 - 60 mm thick, tested under tensile stress (ISO 527), showed a progressive reduction in resistance as the TPPS content increased, although with values suitable (>20 MPa) for food packaging applications. The formulations with 2.5%wt. of lignin-based additives improved functional properties such as antioxidant activity (RSA +78% after 3h), oxygen barrier (OTR +10%), surface wettability (CA -5%) compared to the matrix.

Figure 1. Film samples: a) visual observation, b) tensile strength, c) RSA, d) OTR, e) CA

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DEVELOPMENT OF ACTIVE FILM BASED ON PBS/HOPS BY PRODUCT Hops by product composition and film characterization

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Agri-food by-products have gained significant attention as a promised resource in biodegradable packaging production [1]. Hop (*Humulus lupulus* L.) plant, in all its parts, is a precious source of bioactive compounds [2]. In the process of growing hops, a significant amount of plant material (about 2.6 kg/plant) is used by growers for making compost, but its potential uses haven't been fully explored yet. On the other hand, using bio-based polymers such as polybutylene succinate (PBS) is attracting increasing attention as a valid sustainable and biodegradable plastic alternative. Based on these considerations, the work object is to develop a biodegradable active film based on hop by-products and PBS. The fresh hop by-products, including branches, leaves, and discarded cones, were low-temperature dried and milled to obtain hop by-product powder (HBP). HBP was divided into different fractions according to fiber size (short 63-160 μ m; medium 160-220 μ m; long 220-710 μ m) and characterized in terms of chemical and physical properties. For film preparation, PBS and 10 wt.% of each hop fraction were melt-blended, pelletized, and then compression-molded into thin sheets. Mechanical, thermal and water sorption analyses were performed to evaluate the impact of HBP granulometry on film properties. The antioxidant capacity of the films was evaluated by DPPH and ABTS test after contact with an ethanolic solution and different food simulants. HBP fractions differed in terms of hemicellulose, lignin and cellulose content. The total (poly)phenol content and antioxidant activity of HBP decreased with increasing particle size. The elastic modulus of the film was preserved despite some material embrittlement. The inclusion of HBP increased the water absorption of films, especially when short fibers were used. HBP incorporated into PBS retained its antioxidant activity and demonstrated a good release rate into the food simulants. Results suggested that HBP can be used to generate PBS films with enhanced functionality, which could be suitable for food packing.

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SAFETY OF PBSA AND PBAT FOR FOOD PACKAGING: IDENTIFICATION OF SEMIVOLATILE COMPOUNDS BY GC-MS

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The growing demand for ecofriendly food packaging materials has led to the use of biodegradable polymers like PBSA (polybutylene succinate-co-adipate) and PBAT (polybutylene adipate-co-terephthalate). Although these materials offer environmental advantages, it is essential to assess their safety and the potential migration of chemicals to ensure they are safe for food contact. In this regard, identifying semi-volatile compounds is crucial, as these chemicals may transfer into food and affect human health. This study focused on tentatively identifying and comparing the semi volatile compound profiles in *PBSA* and *PBAT* using gas chromatography – mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and also estimate their toxicity using an *in silico* tool (i.e. Toxtree).

PBSA and PBAT compounds were extracted using methanol at 40°C for 24 hours in sealed vials. The extracts were filtered and analyzed by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) using a Rxi-5Sil MS column (30 m x 0.25 mm internal diameter x 0.25 µm film thickness). The oven temperature was programmed to increase from 40°C to 300°C, and chromatograms were acquired in full-scan mode (m/z range: 35–500).

The analysis revealed the predominant presence of esters, alkanes, alcohols, ketones, amides, and aromatic compounds, associated with antioxidant degradation products and residual additives. Esters stand out as a significant chemical family in both materials, related to the chemical structure of bioplastics.

The semi-volatile compounds identified are mostly classified as Class I and Class III in both materials. In the PBSA material, there was a higher presence of Class I compounds, while in the PBAT material, Class III (high toxicity) compounds predominated. Most of the volatiles tentatively identified are not included in regulation 10/2011 (EU).

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NEW FLEXIBLE PACKAGING SOLUTION FOR SPACE MISSION

A multidisciplinary approach for packaging in space food

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The aerospace food packaging sector is high-tech and highly specialized. Packaging solutions for food are consumed in space and aviation environments, such as long-duration space missions or military and commercial flights. This segment includes packaging that ensures food safety, freshness, and nutrition in extreme conditions of temperature, pressure, and gravity.

Key features of aerospace food packaging include:

- **Lightweight and Durability:** Packaging must be lightweight to reduce the overall load on flights but also highly durable to protect the contents in harsh environments.
- **Advanced Materials:** High-tech materials, such as multi-layer barrier films and high-resistance plastics, are used to maintain food quality over long periods without refrigeration.
- **Hermetic Sealing:** Packaging must be airtight to prevent food spoilage and exposure to external elements.
- **Sustainability:** There is growing attention to eco-friendly materials to reduce waste, even during space missions [1].

The focus is on developing packaging for Mars missions, where extended shelf life, lightweight materials (such as flexible packaging), and waste reduction are critical. Technologies being researched include aluminum oxide-coated plastic laminates and active flexible packaging to reduce microorganism growth. The use of innovative, sustainable packaging materials helps minimize waste and optimize resource use during missions. These efforts are part of broader strategies to make space exploration more environmentally friendly and viable for long-term missions—such as those planned for Mars—where resupply opportunities are limited, and waste management is crucial.

Space agencies are actively implementing policies and programs to ensure the well-being of astronauts during missions, recognizing the physical and psychological challenges of space exploration. These policies support astronauts' mental health, physical fitness, and overall quality of life, especially during long-duration missions. Agencies like NASA and ESA ensure that astronauts have access to a variety of nutritious foods, with special attention to providing comfort foods that support psychological well-being. The taste, smell, and texture of familiar dishes can evoke positive memories, reducing stress and homesickness [2].

The research team is working on innovative flexible packaging based on an innovative biobased film provided from Relicta srl that, compared to conventional packaging, offers a sustainable, waste-free alternative that enhances mission efficiency and the astronaut experience. Additionally, by eliminating traditional packaging waste, this solution reduces the accumulation of non-recyclable material in space, addressing sustainability and waste disposal challenges, thus adding significant value to space exploration logistics.

As part of its spin-in activities in packaging, Sudalimenta has decided to innovate both in the choice of materials and in the end-of-life of the product. According to Sudalimenta, space food packaging must be lightweight, resistant to radiation that can alter taste and significantly reduce nutritional properties, and sustainable in terms of raw materials. Additionally, it must be recyclable or reusable. The prerogatives of recyclability for terrestrial packaging—achievable with the use of

monomaterials-can be transferred to space food packaging while still guaranteeing the required specifications. Furthermore, the packaging enables the consumption of a hot meal regardless of the use of additional equipment or ingredients.

As part of its spin-off activities, Sudalimenta's innovation in packaging, which allows a dish to be stored for a long time and in the smallest possible space, has also generated interest for home use, but even more so for outdoor applications. The "Tiberino 1888" brand, in collaboration with Sudalimenta, has developed a new line of products called "Outfood," which stems from its experience with astronauts. Having served the space sector, the company now offers food solutions for hiking, boating, camping, climbing, caving, extreme cycling, and for those who simply enjoy spending their free time outdoors.

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SMART PH-SENSITIVE INDICATORS BASED ON CURCUMIN AND LAMBRUSCO EXTRACT

A novel tool to track the freshness of pink shrimps

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Food quality control is of crucial importance to protect consumers against foodborne illness [1]. The new packaging defined as active and intelligent can better ensure food traceability and improve food preservation reacting to alterations in the inner atmosphere of the packaging through an easy visual detection of the food quality throughout storage and transportation [2]. Users can then discriminate between fresh and spoiled food [3]. For example, pH indicator-based packaging, which can react to pH changes produced by food decay, is considered a novel intelligent packaging [4]. Therefore, this research is focused on the formulation of novel visual pH-sensitive indicators based on natural extracts from Curcuma Long and Lambrusco wine pomace incorporated into rice starch/pectin/alginate matrixes for non-destructively detecting shrimps freshness in real-time. The effect of either a single natural indicator or their combination was studied and correlated to the properties of the materials. Films were widely characterized in terms of morphological, barrier, spectroscopic, thermal and mechanical properties. Moreover, the pH-sensitive systems showed a noticeable antioxidant and antibacterial activity towards *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. Besides, the mixed indicator-based film showed high sensitivity to ammonia (68%) determining an ΔE value detectable easily by the human eye. Trial tests were conducted to monitor the shelf-life of pink shrimp over time, proving the effectiveness of using the fabricated films for tracking the spoilage of fish at $T=4^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T=25^{\circ}\text{C}$. The colour changes were recorded simultaneously and the turning to deeper colours indicated the decomposition of proteins to organic amines and the spoilage of food. Results show that the produced films provide easily detectable colour changes during food spoilage as tools for multi-purpose intelligent food packaging applications.

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HRT™ FOR SOLVENT RECOVERY PLANT

The new invention for Activated Carbon Regeneration

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The HRT™ invention introduces a significant advancement in solvent recovery plants, particularly in the regeneration of activated carbon beds used for solvent adsorption.

Activated carbon is essential in adsorbing solvents, but over time, these carbon beds require regeneration. The invention focuses on improving the efficiency of both the adsorption and regeneration processes of the solvent recovery plants by utilizing inert gas (nitrogen) for the regeneration of carbon beds, resulting in enhanced operational performance for solvent recovery plants. The invention is dedicated to the plants where the solvents are prior adsorbed to activated carbon beds that, after several hours in adsorption, must be regenerated.

The core target of the HRT™ patent is to address the limitations of existing technologies in the adsorption and regeneration stages. In fact, current systems often face challenges such as inefficient regeneration, high operational costs, and lengthy processing times. The HRT™ invention provides a novel solution to overcome these issues, optimizing both adsorption and regeneration. When the adsorption process for recovery of solvents is performed in accordance with this invention, it avoids the disadvantages of the prior art and provides for the highly advantageous results.

The novel features which are considered as characteristic for HRT™ invention are set forth in particular in the appended claims included in the patent. Essentially, the HRT™ patent aims to bring the following benefits to the plants:

- a) Reduction of the activated carbon bed height in vertical adsorbers, thanks to very fast regeneration of the activated carbon beds – 5% less than standard technology
- b) Increase in the recovery efficiency of the activated carbon bed – 3% activated carbon absorption capacity increasing in comparison with standard technology
- c) Reduction of the total regeneration time of the carbon bed – 40% time reduction
- d) Recovered solvent with water content < 1% - without molecular sieves
- e) Reduction of the Residual Solvent Load at the end of the carbon bed regeneration
- f) Drastically reduction of the running costs of the plant – 35% operating cost reduction
- g) Reduction of CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere thanks to heat recovery implemented with HRT Technology, in the bed regeneration system - 13% emission reduction
- h) Systems environmentally friendly
- i) Compliance with stringent VOC emission regulations as per the limits imposed in the BAT 2024 of the 2010/75/EU
- j) Quick ROI

Testing conducted on existing installations has demonstrated the effectiveness of the HRT system, confirming its ability to optimize solvent recovery, reduce operational costs, and promote sustainability. In conclusion, the HRT invention improves both operational efficiency and environmental performance, offering an innovative solution for solvent recovery plants in terms of running costs and circular economy.

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POLYETHYLENE TEREPHTHALATE- AND PAPER-BASED FLEXIBLE PACKAGING MATERIALS FUNCTIONALIZED WITH SOL-GEL COATINGS

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The food packaging industry is evolving to meet demands for circularity, cost-effectiveness, a lower carbon footprint, and higher production efficiency, with polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and paper emerging as preferred materials. Despite its advantages, PET faces two main challenges in flexible barrier packaging applications, such as flow packs or form-fill-seal pouches. PET films for flexible packaging often lack adequate moisture and oxygen barriers, limiting their range of applications. Additionally, the high melting temperature of PET, around 250°C, complicates the sealing process, leading to deformation and poor-quality seals. Traditional solutions involve multilayer films, where PET is laminated with materials that offer superior permeation barriers and include a lower melting temperature heat-sealing layer. This results in multi-material, non-recyclable packaging, posing sustainability issues. For paper-based flexible materials, their appealing sustainability profile is compromised by the use of laminated fossil-based polymer films or liquid polymer dispersion barrier coatings. These barrier coatings constitute a significant fraction of the packaging material weight and reduce the recyclability of paper. Moreover, PFAS-containing barrier coatings, which are detrimental to health and banned in most EU countries, are still used in the paper industry due to the lack of suitable alternatives. In the present work, PET-based heat-sealable films and high-barrier paper were developed to address these issues. A water-based organic-inorganic hybrid nano-composite sol-gel coating, approximately 2 μm thick, was applied to one side of the 23- μm thick PET film. This coating reduced oxygen and water vapor transmission rates of PET by more than a factor of 3 and 4, respectively, and enhanced the mechanical strength of the film, enabling higher quality heat sealing (Figure 1). The same sol-gel coating was used to prime the 70 gsm paper prior to the deposition of a 2 μm thick layer of another hybrid sol-gel coating, adding enhanced barriers. The barrier properties of the coated paper, shown in Figure 2, are KIT 9, Cobb1800 of 1 g/m^2 , OTR of 18 $\text{ml}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$, and WVTR of 26 $\text{g}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$ at 23°C, 50% RH. These coatings can be applied using conventional techniques and are curable like traditional water-based inks, making them suitable for industrial applications. Furthermore, the developed coated films and paper are easier to recycle than state-of-the-art flexible multi-materials, enhancing packaging material circularity and aligning with sustainability goals in food packaging.

Figure 1. Heat-sealed PET films with and without sol-gel coating.

Figure 2. Drops of crude oil persisting on the paper surface treated with sol-gel coatings.

BIOINSPIRED HYBRID COATING VIA SOL-GEL SYNTHESIS

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The packaging industry increasingly seeks innovative and sustainable solutions that combine high performance with environmental responsibility. In this context, bioinspired design represents an innovative approach to developed sustainable yet multifunctional barrier layer¹. A compelling example is the plant’s cuticle, an extracellular membrane which provides hydrophobicity and transpiration capabilities^{2,3}.

The present work aims at developing a hybrid coating with hydro-repellent properties by introducing a nature-derived hydroxy fatty acid, 16-Hexadecanoic acid (HHA) and glycerol in a classic sol-gel route and then deposited by rod coater on corona-treated polymeric substrates. TEOS and GLYMO have been selected as network forming and modifier, respectively. The surface morphology was studied using SEM and profilometer revealing a close resemblance with the typical plant’s cuticle, whilst the presence of silane spherulite structures was detected for increased glycerol content. The water contact angle (WCA) has been measured on uncoated and coated samples. PET substrate showed an initial WCA around 75° increased up to 22° after depositing hybrid coating with HHA. The oxygen transmission rate (OTR) of pristine PET has been reduced after depositing hybrid coating with HHA and Glycerol by 54%; carbon dioxide transmission rate (CO₂TR) decreases by 44%, while the water vapor transmission rate (WVTR) registered a reduction of 31%. Similar improvements have been registered after depositing the coatings on BOPP substrates. The presence of micro-cracks, reduced by adding Glycerol, hinder potential barrier capabilities.

The coating’s structure and bonding were assessed by EDS and FT-IR analysis. Presence of stretching vibrations in the range of 1029 cm⁻¹ confirms the silica network formation while the presence of CH stretching vibration demonstrates that HHA crystalizes during synthesis. This finding is further cemented by the melting peaks detected during the differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis. In conclusion, the bioinspired hybrid coatings developed by introducing HHA crystals in organically modified silica network can be an ideal candidate to provide commercial polymeric substrates with important multifunctionalities. Barrier properties towards key permeants of coated samples are an improvement over pristine polymeric substrates, while the coating’s morphology reduced PET hydrophilicity. Moreover, the obtained coating’s morphology represents a novel structure that can be further optimized through the selection of alternative alkoxides, different organic/inorganic ratios, or thermal treatment.

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THE BENEFITS OF FLEXO PLATE MICROCELL PATTERNING

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Abstract

Flexography is a rotary printing process that uses flexible relief plates and is commonly used for printing on packaging, labels and other substrates. Flexo plates can be manufactured to have graded microcell patterning superimposed on the individual dot heads to control the ink spread and hence print quality. There are several hypotheses as to the mechanisms of inking and ink release [1], however this topic is underexplored in the literature. This study explores the impact of microcell patterning on ink transfer and print quality as well as the interaction between microcell patterns, ink types, plate materials, and anilox. Water-based ink was selected for its environmental benefits, while UV ink was used to evaluate the role of microcells in managing solvent loss and print quality. BOPP and coated polyester substrates were chosen for their industry relevance, using ASAHI water-washable photopolymer plates [2] with varying boost settings and dot technologies to assess the optimal configuration for ink transfer. Two Anilox rolls with different ink volumes (3.5 cm³/m² and 5.5 cm³/m²) were tested to evaluate their effect on ink distribution.

Additives such as extender and retarder interact with the ink's components, significantly influencing ink rheology and hence printability. The Asahi boost had a minimal impact on solid area ink transfer, which was primarily determined by ink viscoelasticity. Unlike UV inks, water-based inks exhibit a Saffman and Taylor ink splitting mechanism in solid and micro-celled patterns [3]. At 50% halftone, solid dot patterns with water-based inks transfer more ink, producing larger, thicker dots, while microcell patterns transfer less ink, resulting in smaller dots. Microcells help control dot gain but reduce ink transfer at lower halftones. The more viscous UV inks deliver higher colour density and produce larger dots with more consistent ink transfer. The UV microcell pattern prints were thicker than non-microcell patterns, controlling ink spread but lowering overall ink coverage, while non-microcell solid dot patterns had thinner printed dots with lower ink coverage.

The CrysC9 microcell dot pattern consisted of micro cell dots with the most consistent dot pattern when compared to the other 3 microcell dots. The CrysC9 microcell pattern increases ink transfer but leads to over-inked dots. Comparing ink types, UV ink at 1.6% halftones produces larger and denser prints with a larger dot diameter than water-based ink. Both inks create dots closer to the target 1.6% with the solid (no MC) Circ dot pattern. This study highlights the potential of microcell patterning in optimizing ink transfer, improving dot quality, and offering a method for better print consistency in flexographic printing.

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SUPPORTING TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION FOR FOOD CONTACT MATERIALS (FCM): CAST project

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The Supporting Documentation (DS) to the Declaration of Compliance (DoC) of Materials and Articles in Contact with Food (FCM) is an obligation for Business Operators, to provide evidence of the compliance with applicable legislation.

Contrary to the DoC, the DS does not accompany the goods and there is no obligation to deliver it to the customer. The DS shall be available to the Competent Authorities, on demand, to demonstrate correct management of the manufacturing process (GMP Regulation, 2023/2006/EC) and the safety and quality of the products (Reg 1935/2004/EC). This applies to all the sectors and to all the manufacturing stages of FCM.

In the absence of a harmonized standard to prepare the SD, the Italian CAST Project has been working since 2009, to develop and make available “shared” Guidelines. The innovative tool of the CAST Project is the fusion of knowledge between public and private stakeholders to identify shared methodologies of approach to food safety and technical solutions that can form a common basis between private and public sectors.

The main achievements of the project, with respect the DS, is a series of shared Guidelines. All the Guidelines, including that on DS, are divided into three parts:

Part A. General Guideline - General section on supporting documentation (legislative references and general applications).

Part B. Specific Guidelines - Specific section on supporting documentation (implementations that supply chains carry out to ensure compliance with legislative requirements).

Part C. Use of non-legislative documents in evaluation processes

In the SD a number of information should be reported e.g. compositional tests, risk assessments, analytical screenings, GMP files, etc. The quality and quantity of "pertinent" information in the SD strictly depends on the nature of the material and its intended use, but also on the position of the Business in the supply chain.

The paper will present the CAST approach for FCM made of plastic mono and multilayers, as such and/or coupled with other materials.

The published CAST Guidelines are freely available as ISTISAN Reports (www.iss.it)

FOOD CONTACT MATERIALS (FCM)

Effect of Measurement of Uncertainty on Compliance with the Regulation (EU) 10/2011

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This paper deals with the impact of measurement uncertainty on the compliance of plastic Food Contact Materials and article (FCMs). In fact, plastic (FCM) fall within the scope of application of Regulation (EU) 10/2011[1], that establishes requirements such as Overall Migration Limit (OML) and Specific Migration Limits (SML) to guarantee a food safety using plastic FCM.

Furthermore, the EC provision requires to calculate the measurement uncertainty of the analytical measures. This is also a requirement under ISO/IEC 17025 [2] norm. In short, laboratories must evaluate their measurement uncertainty (MU) and apply a documented decision rule when making declaration or statements of compliance. To conform with this requirement, different approaches may be adopted that may significantly diverge among the analytical laboratories with a consequent possible difference in the interpretation of compliance. On the other hand, neither unique and uniform approach is available in the field of plastic FCM, nor a sounded study the impact of measurement uncertainty on compliance with legal limit are available. This situation leaves a technical-decisional gap that needs to be addressed.

Currently, to estimate the measurement uncertainty and to select appropriate decision rules, several documents and guidelines are available such as Eurachem/CITAC, Nordest, Eurolab and ILAC [3-6]. By and large, in these documents and in scientific literature two main approaches are used to estimate the uncertainty:

- a) the bottom-up modelling approach, that gives evaluations of all the uncertainty components by using the law of propagation of error of error
- b) the empirical top-down approach, that is based on quality control and validation data.

This paper presents several case studies in which the uncertainties are calculated and applied in the decision on compliance to SML. Their effect is extensively discussed.

It is noted that the estimation of uncertainty and the implemented decisional rule become crucial to the interpretation of results, not only for enforcement purposes, but also for the private laboratories, especially when analytical results are close to the legal limit as well as when the uncertainty figure is particularly high.

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INNOVATIVE ECO-FRIENDLY MATERIALS IN FOOD CONTACT OVERALL MIGRATION

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This paper presents an analytical study on innovative and eco-friendly Food Contact Materials (FCM), developed to promote a circular economy and the objectives of the European Green Deal as well. In this context, reducing waste and adopting sustainable practices along the production chain highlight the need for continuous research on new sustainable materials. These materials and articles have to comply with the safety requirements established by the Framework Regulation (EC) 1935/2004 [1].

Independently from the nature of the material, to ensure food safety, the release of components should be prevented or minimized to guarantee a certain degree of chemical inertness. To this aim, as regards plastic FCM, the Regulation (EU) 10/2011 [2] establishes that the measure of chemical inertness is the analytical determination of the Overall Migration. Hence, Overall Migration Limits (OMLs) are provided, expressed as 10 mg/dm² or 60 mg/kg food, depending on their characteristic.

The study presented in this paper deals with the characterization of the composition of a number of FCM present on the market with “eco or bio” claims. Fourier Transform Infrared – Attenuated Total Reflectance Spectroscopy (FT/IR-ATR) was used for this task. Subsequently, the selected FCM were submitted to Overall Migration testing. According to the intended use of the FCM (labels or foreseeable use) different food simulants and real use conditions were applied, following the indications given by JRC 134290 guideline [3] on testing conditions.

The results are discussed with respect the nature of the material versus the eco-friendly claim, and the suitability of the OM testing.

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MIGRATION FROM PLASTIC FOOD CONTACT MATERIALS NIAS and OLIGOMERS

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In these recent years, the public concern in Non Intentionally Added Substances (NIAS), migratable from Food Contact Materials (FCM), has grown. According to the Regulation (EU) 10/2011 [1] on plastic FCM, NIAS are “*an impurity in the substances used or a reaction intermediate formed during the production process or a decomposition or reaction product*”. It is stated that NIAS, although not included in the Union list of the authorised substances, may be present in the plastic layers of plastic materials or articles (article 6). Furthermore, their compliance with Article 3 of Regulation (EC) 1935/2004 [2] shall be assessed in accordance with internationally recognised scientific principles on risk assessment (Reg. (EU) 10/2011, article 19), as well as for other substances that are not covered by an inclusion in the Union List but that may be used/present. There is currently no systematic approach agreed among analytical laboratories to test the safety of plastic FCM for NIAS. In this concern, this paper presents an approach to produce experimental data, aimed to contribute to the knowledge of this topic but also to the specific in house monitoring or official control activities.

Thirty-three plastic FCM articles (single-use) were purchased on the market. Various types of articles (trays, cups, containers) made of different plastics (i.e. polyesters, polystyrenes, “eco”-plastics, polyolefins) have been selected; two additional plastic coated cellulose articles (cups) were also get. All FCM articles were firstly characterized to identify their materials by Raman spectroscopy and by Fourier Transform Infra Red - Attenuated Total Reflectance spectroscopy (FT/IR-ATR).

Subsequently, 21 samples was submitted to migration tests: food simulant D1 (Ethanol 50%) was used and test conditions according to JRC 134290 guideline [3] have been applied. Overall migration tests were performed, too. A characterization screening was carried out by GC/MS, for the detection of NIAS migrated in the simulant solutions, after extraction with isooctane. A research by UPLC-MS/MS was carried out also on PET samples to characterize and quantify PET oligomers. The possible origin of the identified substances has been investigated and an attribution was attempted, based on literature references, web search and previous scientific knowledge. This research was carried out within the scope of the Current Research Project PRC IZSLER 2020/001.

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EXPLORING SODA CONTAMINATION COMING FROM PAPER STRAWS

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1. Introduction

The adoption of Directive (EU) 2019/904 has driven a significant shift from plastic to paper straws as part of broader efforts to mitigate environmental impacts. While paper straws are considered environmentally sustainable due to their biodegradability, concerns have emerged regarding the potential migration of volatile and non-volatile chemical compounds into beverages. This issue arises from the chemical composition of paper straws, which often includes adhesives, coatings, and inks. Compared to plastics, the study of chemical migration from paper-based materials remains underexplored, necessitating a more comprehensive examination, particularly in the context of printed straws used with carbonated beverages. The complex formulations of inks, comprising pigments, binders, solvents, and other additives, pose risks of releasing harmful substances during use. Advanced analytical methodologies, such as Ultra-High-Pressure Liquid Chromatography coupled with Ion Mobility Quadrupole Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry (UPLC-IM-QTOF), are crucial for the detection and characterization of these untargeted compounds. This research aims to address the safety implications of such migrations and contribute to closing regulatory gaps in the oversight of paper-based food contact materials.

2. Materials and Methods

Nine different printed straws from various suppliers were studied. Straws were acquired from three local supermarkets. Migration studies were done with a carbonated drink (soda). The migration studies were set-up according document by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre. The migration analyses were performed using UPLC-IM-Q/TOF.

3. Results and Methods

The migration solutions were analyzed using UPLC-IM-Q/TOF, a technique that enhances separation. The migration solutions obtained from the paper straws were analyzed using ultra-performance liquid chromatography coupled with ion mobility-quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry (UPLC-IM-Q/TOF). This state-of-the-art analytical technique provided an additional separation dimension via drift time, effectively minimizing interferences caused by coeluting compounds within complex soda matrices. By aligning precursor and fragment ions in both retention time and drift time, the analysis achieved a higher level of precision, ensuring robust identification and quantification of migrating compounds. Data processing involved peak detection and componentization, which utilized both retention time and drift time alignment. These components were then subjected to Principal Component Analysis (PCA), which identified patterns and correlations within the dataset. PCA proved particularly effective in distinguishing samples by supplier and even identified variations within products from the same manufacturer. For instance, while samples G1 and G2, as well as G3 and G5, grouped together according to their respective manufacturers, sample G4, obtained from the same supplier as G3 and G5, exhibited a distinct migration profile. This divergence was attributed to differences in ink composition, underscoring the significant influence of ink and coatings on migration behavior. The combination of PCA with Orthogonal Projection to Latent Structures Discriminant Analysis (OPLS-DA) enabled deeper insights into the markers driving these distinctions. The S-plot derived from OPLS-DA identified specific markers responsible for the observed discrepancies, highlighting compounds that were either unique to or present at elevated levels in particular samples.

The compounds identified through this approach included several known additives and non-intentionally added substances (NIAS) commonly associated with plastic products, such as tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate, bis(2-ethylhexyl) sebacate, dioctyl phthalate, and 3-hydroxy-2,2,4-trimethylpentyl isobutyrate. Compound identification relied on an extensive database of over 10,000 food contact material-related substances, incorporating retention time, accurate mass, and collision cross-section (CCS) values. This database, developed by Song et al. (2022), allowed for precise matching of compounds migrating from the paper straws into the soda. Identifications were further validated using pure standard analyses to confirm the compounds' presence. Quantification was achieved through calibration curves, with specific migration limits evaluated based on Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 and the Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC) concept proposed by EFSA (2019). This regulatory framework provided provisional benchmarks for determining the safety of the migrating substances. The results raised concerns regarding the food safety of paper straws, as several migrating substances detected were additives typically used in plastics. For instance, oleamide, N,N-ethylenebis stearamide, and other plasticizers were identified, suggesting that paper straws may not inherently be a safer alternative to plastic straws.

Fig. 1. Scores plot obtained from the Principal Component Analysis for the three replicates of each sample analyzed.

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UNTARGETED SCREENING OF PERFLUOROALKYL SUBSTANCES AND BISPHENOLS IN FOOD CONTACT MATERIALS

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Poly- and perfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) are a family of several thousand fluorinated aliphatic compounds used in hundreds of industrial products such as fire-fighting foams, coatings and paper products for food packaging [1]. Early studies on this class of compounds focused on perfluoroalkyl acids (PFAA), like perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS) and perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA). In 2006 the European Commission limited the use of these substances [2], in the same year US EPA launched a global stewardship program inviting companies to reduce PFOA [3]. Following these regulations that limited their use, industries searched for alternative fluorinated compounds, like perfluoroalkyl sulfonates and perfluoroalkyl ether carboxylic acids (e.g., GenX, ADONA and F-53B) [4]. Other emerging categories of compounds are fluorotelomers and fluorinated polymers, substances with high molecular weight that can degrade over time and lead to the formation of PFCAs [5].

Nowadays, over 9,000 PFAS have been identified, and this number is rapidly increasing.

Bisphenol A (BPA) is commonly used in the production of various products because it provides strength and durability to the finished items. It is commonly found in polycarbonate plastics. BPA is also a key component in epoxy resins. Additionally, it is used in the manufacturing of certain types of inks and adhesives, enhancing their durability and adhesion properties. Despite its widespread use, BPA has raised health concerns because it can act as an endocrine disruptor, leading to increased scrutiny and the development of BPA-free alternatives in consumer goods. [6] In June 2024, the European Commission proposed a draft regulation to ban the use of Bisphenol A (BPA) and other bisphenols and their derivatives in food contact materials. Consequently, the existing Specific Migration Limit (SML) for BPA, currently set at 0.05 mg/kg, will be updated. [7] Up to now, the ECHA and Member States have assessed 148 different bisphenols and recommended restrictions on more than 30 of them due to their potential hormonal or reprotoxic effects.

Liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry is often used for the determination of PFAS and Bisphenols in food contact materials. The increasing necessity to monitor a large number of these compounds highlights the need for an untargeted approach using high-resolution mass spectrometry. A specialized instrumental library is also crucial to achieve the target to identify the largest number of fluorinated molecules.

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TOXICOLOGICAL RISK ASSESSMENT OF NIAS

How to assess the substances potentially migrating from the packaging to the food

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European Regulation 1935/2004 is the foundation of community guidelines and ruling, and sets out the general requirements to be met by all the materials and articles intended for food contact. In particular, the packaging should not constitute a risk to human health. European Regulation 10/2011 is the first regulation to introduce the term NIAS (Non-Intentionally Added Substance) and establish the obligation for the manufacturer to carry out risk assessment of these substances in accordance with internationally recognized scientific principles, although it does not provide specific guidelines. In recent years, several independent organizations have published detailed guidelines on toxicological risk assessments for food contact materials. Despite this, the Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC) approach – gathered from *in silico* tools - is often applied without fully considering the toxicological properties of the NIAS: actually, the toxicological properties predicted by *in silico* tools, such as OECD QSAR Toolbox or ToxTree, should be reviewed and interpreted by qualified experts to ensure their accuracy and relevance. The goal of the presentation is to clarify the distinction between risk assessment and the concept of 'hazard,' share information to enable a more informed and precise use of common *in silico* tools, and explain how to conduct a tailored evaluation by deriving the Specific Migration Limit (SML) from publicly available information on substances using scientific and rigorous methods. This approach allows for the derivation of an SML that closely reflects the actual toxicological profile of the NIAS of interest, thereby facilitating the execution of the risk assessment. [1] The main focus of the presentation is on the evaluation of NIAS from plastic material, using examples elaborated by our team, with a special focus on oligomers [2,3,4] and on Substances of Very High Concern [5,6]. Another example will cover the evaluation of Bismuth from metal [7]. The presentation aims to provide a robust framework for the assessment of NIAS, contributing to the overall safety and regulatory compliance of food contact materials. Attendees will gain insights into the latest methodologies and regulatory requirements, enhancing their understanding of how to effectively manage the risks associated with NIAS impurities.

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THE INTERACTION BETWEEN ETHANOL AND ETHYL ACETATE IN THE COMBUSTION OF THEIR MIXTURES IN AIR

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Ethanol-ethyl acetate mixtures are widely used as solvents in the packaging industry. These mixtures are characterized by relatively low values of flash point (even lower than ethanol and ethyl acetate [1]), which make them highly prone to generating explosive conditions. Hence, dedicated investigations on the combustion/explosion behavior of ethanol-ethyl acetate mixtures are imperative to elucidate their safety implications. For ethanol and, mostly, ethyl acetate, the lack of data mainly concerns explosion characteristics other than laminar burning velocity. Conversely, for ethanol-ethyl acetate mixtures, there also exists a substantial absence of information concerning this parameter [2,3].

In this work, the laminar burning velocity, S_L , of ethanol-ethyl acetate mixtures in air was investigated (at 90 °C and atmospheric pressure) through computations performed using three different detailed chemical kinetic mechanisms, and measurements obtained from pressure time histories recorded during closed vessel explosion experiments. Computations were run varying the equivalence ratio, ϕ , from 0.6 to 1.7, and the mole fraction of ethanol in the fuel mixture from 0 (only ethyl acetate) to 1 (only ethanol). For all systems, explosion experiments were carried out at $\phi = 1.1$, i.e., the composition at which, according to calculations, S_L achieves its maximum value. Regardless of the kinetic mechanism, reasonable agreement is found between computed and experimental data, including experimental data retrieved from the literature for ethanol and ethyl acetate. Results show that the behavior of ethanol-ethyl acetate is bounded between the behaviors of ethanol and ethyl acetate, approaching the former/latter as the mixture is enriched in ethanol/ethyl acetate. Over the whole range of equivalence ratios explored, the values of S_L for ethanol-ethyl acetate are smaller than those obtained by averaging the corresponding values of ethanol and ethyl acetate according to their mole proportions in the fuel mixture. This is also confirmed experimentally. A simple Le Chatelier's mixing rule-like formula is proved to predict values of S_L that closely match both computed and experimental data, suggesting that the nature of the interaction between ethanol and ethyl acetate is predominantly thermal rather than chemical.

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BISPHENOL A DIGLYCIDYL ETHER BEHAVIOUR DURING DIGESTION

First approach using a semi-dynamic *in vitro* protocol

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Chemicals from materials used as coatings for metal cans must not migrate into the food in quantities that may pose a risk to the health of consumers. Given the growing concern over the presence of BPA derivatives in epoxy resins used in cans (1), *in vitro* digestion protocols serve as a tool to estimate exposure and assess the bioaccessibility of these substances. For the first time in this application, a semi-dynamic version of INFOGEST has been selected to achieve precise control over parameters such as pH, temperature, and the addition of digestive fluids (2).

The aim of this work was to evaluate the bioaccessibility of bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (BADGE), one of the main substances present in epoxy resins, and observe its transformations during gastrointestinal digestion.

With the purpose of understanding the influence of the food matrix, these experiments were conducted in the presence of olive oil, a representative fatty food. To simulate the long-term storage to which cans are exposed, an interaction test with the food matrix was performed at 60°C for 10 days prior to the digestion assay. Furthermore, to represent different age groups, the gastric phases of each digestion were performed at pH values 1, 2, 3, and 4. A suitable chromatographic method was used to quantify the compounds of interest and identify the products formed during the digestion process. The results of the interaction test showed a similar recovery of BADGE compared to room temperature. However, the bioaccessibility rates were significantly reduced after the interaction test, with values below 50% at all tested gastric pH levels compared to those obtained at room temperature. The highest recovery values were obtained during digestions with a gastric pH of 2, consistent with the results previously observed under static conditions. The digestion process contributes to BADGE release from food matrix increasing its bioaccessibility and consequently the human exposure.

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RISK ASSESSMENT OF MIGRATION IN RECYCLED POLYPROPYLENE

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1. Introduction

The accumulation of plastic waste in the environment has become an increasingly pressing issue. To address this challenge, the European Union has identified the circular economy as a key strategy, with recycling prioritized as the foremost solution for managing post-consumer plastic packaging waste. However, polyolefins such as polypropylene (PP), high-density polyethylene (HDPE) have yet to achieve successful recycling for food contact applications. This is primarily due to their significant potential for chemical diffusion and the absence of suitable technologies specifically tailored to these materials.

2. Materials and Methods

Seven different pellets made from post-consumer polypropylene (PP) from various countries were studied. These pellets were produced using different recycling technologies. The migration behavior of these materials was evaluated in various food simulants to identify volatile and non-volatile compounds that migrated, with the aim of optimizing the recycling processes. The migration analyses were performed using GC-MS and UPLC-MS/QTO

3. Results and Discussion

Fifteen migrated compounds were identified, including known additives such as various antioxidants (Irganox 1010, Irgafos 168, PS802, Irganox 3114), plasticizers (acetyl tributyl citrate), emulsifiers (glycerol monostearate), lubricants (oleamide), and antiblock agents (erucamide). Several NIAS (Non-Intentionally Added Substances) were also detected, including degradation products of antioxidants, reaction products of N,N-Bis(2-Hydroxyethyl)amines with fatty acids, and oligomers from other types of polymers and several residues from cleaning products, detergents and flavoring agents. *Fig. 1.*

Fig1. Migration chromatogram of one sample analyzed by UPLC-MS/QTOF

Significant differences in the number of migrants were observed depending on the type of recycling cleaning technology applied.

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DESIGNING ECO-FRIENDLY COATINGS TO EXTEND THE SHELF LIFE OF POST-HARVEST FRUITS AND VEGETABLES

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Abstract

The experimental work presented in this study is part of the national PRIN EXTRAFRESCO project, which aims to create biopolymeric and bioactive coating formulations for the food packaging industry. These formulations prioritize sustainability while enhancing the post-harvest shelf life of perishable food items. This is particularly important for fruits like strawberries, blueberries, and tomatoes [1,2], which are prone to rapid spoilage after harvest and are often available in limited quantities. Extending their shelf life while preserving their qualitative and nutritional characteristics, such as appearance, color, texture, flavor, firmness, and phytochemical content, is crucial.

This study evaluates various edible coating formulations based on guar gum that was employed as primary substrate for the preparation of edible coating for post harvest strawberries. The addition of several antimicrobial and/or water-repellent agents like chitosan, carnauba wax, beeswax and agro-wastes extracts was evaluated.

As an appropriate viscosity of the coating solutions is important to ensure good adhesiveness to the fruit surface, the role of two plasticizers, glycerol and sorbitol, added at 1 wt.%, was also examined to modulate viscosity the final viscosity of the edible coating.

On the best-performing formulations, the fruit shelf-life was assessed by measuring fruit firmness, decay incidence, weight loss, titratable acidity, and total soluble solids (TSS). It was found that the addition of chitosan together with hemp and wheat bran nutraceutical extracts has proved to be a good approach to improve the strawberries post-harvest shelf-life. The combination of extracts and chitosan having antimicrobial properties significantly improved the strawberry index decay during the storage. Moreover, from the TSS reduction, that is generally correlated to hydrolysis and the utilization of the reducing sugars and acids which are the main substrates in the fruit respiration, remained unvaried until day 6 proving the slowing of strawberry maturation and senescence.

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FLEXIBLE PACKAGING BASED ON NO-MOLD COATINGS FOR BAKERY FOOD

Design and development from lab-scale to industrial application

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Molds compromise food quality by causing visible or invisible defects, such as patches, texture alterations, off-odors, and unpleasant flavors.[1] An innovative technique to remove or inhibit the formation of molds is to coat the packaging material with a polymer containing anti-mold agents that evaporate in the headspace or migrate to the food surface through diffusion.[2] Vanillin is a promising anti-mold agent for bakery products to be incorporated in a coating, as it is considered a safe GRAS additive with demonstrated bioactive, antioxidant and antimicrobial properties against molds and bacteria. [3] In this study, the design and development of no-mold flexible packaging based on polypropylene (PP) is presented. The packaging consists of a PP film coated with vanillin-based formulations applied via rotogravure on the side in direct contact with food, effectively inhibiting mold growth in croissants. The process began by defining the no-mold coating formula, introducing vanillin in commercial coatings (acrylic resins, PVAc). Preliminary tests *in-vitro* (*Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus brasiliensis*, *Penicillium simplicissimum*) validated the no-mold effect increasing the quantity of vanillin in coatings, while the release ability of the coating formula was preliminarily evidenced by FTIR analysis on coated samples. Lab tests helped establish two vanillin-based no-mold formulas. Adhesion, sealing, blocking, and set-off tests on samples prepared using rod coating techniques enabled optimization of the formulations, identifying their advantages and limitations for industrial application. The industrial scale up on rotogravure machine was performed defining the deposition parameters (rate of deposition, drying temperature, coating grammage). Prototypes of the PP reels coated with no-mold formulas were prepared and characterized for coating adhesion, sealing performances, residual solvents content and coefficient of friction. Additionally, the prototypes were successfully tested on an industrial packing machine in collaboration with a bakery company. Inoculated croissants packed using the innovative packaging underwent panel testing and were compared with those packed using traditional packaging. Results showed that the no-mold packaging effectively inhibited mold growth, compared to traditional packaging. These activities are a part of the project “NO MOLD” (2020-2023) (*Integrated approach to the fight against molds and microtoxins in the grain and baked goods sector*), founded by the MISE (Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico) under the grant agreement No 0091978.

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EXTRACTION OF BIOACTIVE MOLECULES FROM AGRO-WASTE FOR FUNCTIONAL COATINGS IN SUSTAINABLE FOOD PRESERVATION

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The increasing global demand for fresh fruits and vegetables has emphasized the need for efficient post-harvest preservation strategies to meet the United Nations' goal of halving per capita food waste by 2030 [1]. In this context, plant-derived extracts and food-waste biomasses offer promising opportunities to develop sustainable, bio-based coating formulations that reduce dependency on fossil resources and promote a circular economy [2].

The first part of the PRIN EXTRAFRESCO project aims to extract and optimize bioactive molecules from underutilized agro-waste, specifically wheat bran and hemp seeds, to create functionalized bio-coatings for the food industry. This study focuses on three extraction methods - ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE), microwave-assisted extraction (MAE), and conventional stirring - using two solvents: water and 50% ethanol (v/v). The extracted compounds were evaluated for phytochemical composition and antioxidant activity through FRAP, DPPH, and ORAC assays. Additionally, the antimicrobial activity of the extracts was tested against pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms. Among the tested solvents, 50% ethanol emerged as the most effective. Microwave-assisted extraction at 70°C provided optimal yields for wheat bran and hemp seeds, while ultrasound showed limited improvements despite variations in time and power settings. Comparatively, new extraction techniques demonstrated greater efficiency, although not statistically significant, achieving higher yields in shorter times than the conventional method. Microbial inhibition assays revealed that wheat bran extracts exhibited a stronger reduction in bacterial growth than hemp seed extracts across all tested strains. These findings highlight the potential of wheat bran and hemp seed extracts as valuable sources of bioactive molecules for antimicrobial applications. Furthermore, once incorporated into edible coating formulations, the cytotoxicity of functionalized coatings was tested on HT-29 cells using the MTT assay to support their safe application in the food industry.

This active coating, enriched with extracted bioactive compounds, will protect fresh food products from oxidative damage and microbial spoilage thereby extending shelf life and reducing food waste.

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TURNING WASTE INTO VALUE: EDIBLE COATINGS FROM AGRI-FOOD BY-PRODUCTS TO EXTEND FRESH PRODUCE SHELF-LIFE

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This study is part of the OnFoods research initiative promoting sustainable food production. It explores the recycling and revaluation of agri-food and forestry by-products using green technologies, aligning with circular economy principles. Additionally, it addresses food waste by developing biocompatible coatings to extend the shelf-life and preserve the quality of perishable foods like fruits and vegetables [1]. Therefore, in this experimental work, we combined extracts obtained from plant-based by-products, with biopolymeric formulations, to create an edible coating that was applied to fresh tomatoes. The studied plant material included bark and branches of European spruce (*Picea abies* L.), chestnut tree (*Castanea sativa* L.) bark, and pomegranate fruit (*Punica granatum* L.) waste, whose extracts, prepared through sustainable extractions (microwave- and ultrasound-assisted), were evaluated for their phytochemical content, antioxidant, and antimicrobial activities. The most promising extracts were subsequently used in chitosan guar gum- and chitosan cassava-based coatings. The coated fresh tomatoes were then analyzed 7 and 30 days after the treatment, to monitor changes in their nutraceutical values and microbial charge. Several attempts were made to assess the optimal extraction condition for each waste material, in terms of solvent, extraction time, temperature, microwave power, and ultrasound amplitude, compared with the traditional maceration extraction. The extracts were evaluated according to their total phenolic and flavonoid contents, and their antioxidant and antiradical activities. Overall, all the waste materials proved to be still a rich source of bioactive compounds. We noticed that the use of microwaves was better than ultrasounds and maceration, while 50% ethanol was shown to be the best solvent for phytochemical extraction. Moreover, all the optimized extracts were generally stable three weeks after preparation. Their antimicrobial activity towards *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, and *Pseudomonas stutzeri* was tested in a microdilution assay (0.75-24 mg/ml). Spruce bark and pomegranate waste-optimized extracts exerted excellent growth-inhibitory activity towards the strains tested, and they were selected to be included in the coating formulations. Tomatoes were analyzed 7 and 30 days after treatment to evaluate the contents of phytochemicals, lycopene, carbohydrates, and antioxidant potential. Slight changes in these parameters were appreciated compared with non-coated or tomatoes-coated with the biopolymer alone. Interestingly, a dramatic reduction of cell densities of aerobic microorganisms was detected in tomatoes subjected to coating treatments including spruce bark and pomegranate extracts after 30 days of storage at room temperature.

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UPCYCLING TOMATO PLANT WASTE INTO SUSTAINABLE AND BIODEGRADABLE 3D-PRINTED FOOD PACKAGING

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Introduction

The growing demand for sustainable packaging solutions has driven research towards bio-based and biodegradable materials derived from agricultural waste [1,2]. This study explores the valorization of tomato plant (*Solanum lycopersicum*) waste as a natural filler in biopolymeric matrices for the production of 3D-printed food packaging.

Materials and Methods

By incorporating tomato plant waste (SLP) into polylactic acid (PLA), Mater-Bi® (MB), and their blend (PLA/MB, 50:50), novel bio-composite filaments were developed and successfully processed through fused deposition modeling (FDM). The preparation process involved the drying, grinding, and sieving of SLP to obtain a fine powder, which was then melt-mixed with the biodegradable polymeric matrices. The resulting filaments were extruded and tested for processability and printability.

Results

All the obtained filaments were successfully printed by FDM, in agreement with morphological analysis and rheological characterization. Morphological analysis performed on the cross section of 3D printed composite samples confirmed a relatively uniform dispersion of the natural filler in all composite samples. Moreover, MB and MB/PLA samples displayed good adhesion between the filler and the matrix, unlike PLA ones where imperfect adhesion was observed. These behaviors affect the mechanical performance of the composites. For MB and MB/PLA the filler effectively acts as reinforcement. SLP elastic modulus was evaluated by powder nanoindentation and, for the majority of the composites, the theoretical Halpin-Tsai model satisfactorily fitted the actual tensile moduli.

Conclusions

These findings highlight the potential of tomato plant waste as a cost-effective, sustainable, and functional additive for the production of biodegradable food packaging, offering an environmentally friendly alternative to petroleum-based plastics.

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INNOVATIVE WATER-BASED COATING FOR FLEXIBLE FILMS

Barrier solutions for sustainable packaging

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Introduction

SAES is an advanced functional materials group that conceives and produces new families of materials bearing special characteristics, which find their application in a variety of areas such as consumer electronics, domotics, automotive, particle accelerators, gas purification and packaging. SAES Packaging Division, through its cutting-edge technology, offers advanced sustainable and efficient solutions able to support flexible packaging industry in the entire supply chain.

Our expertise in advanced materials, surface science and water-based formulations allows us to develop innovative high-performance & eco-friendly barrier coatings that extend product shelf life. Functional coatings are applied by means of high-speed roll-to-roll coating techniques on an extended variety of substrates; the thin thickness of SAES coatings (usually $<1 \mu\text{m}$) enables the downgauging of the packaging and the elimination of multilayer films, making the final product recyclable or compostable.

Transparent multi-gas barrier performances are provided by the synergistic effects of AlO_x layer and water-based coating COATHINK[®] [1] ($\text{OTR} < 0,5 \text{ cc/m}^2 \text{ 24h}$ | $\text{WVTR} < 1 \text{ g/m}^2 \text{ 24h}$). These highly protective products exhibit exceptional optical and mechanical properties compatible with typical converting processes and greater O_2 barrier stability under high RH conditions [2].

The expertise and know-how of SAES in the development and industrialization of sustainable barrier coatings is supporting the development activity of EcoeFISHent European project (Horizon 2020).

EU-funded EcoeFISHent project

EcoeFISHent project aims to demonstrate a replicable systemic and sustainable cluster for territorial deployment of the climate neutral circular economy, by creating six multilevel and synergic circular value chains (CVC) interconnecting blue and green-economies to reconcile human industrial and economic activities with marine ecosystems and marine protected areas.

One of the EcoeFISHent goals is the development of an innovative bio-mass pre-treatment and extraction technologies in order to enable sustainable and efficient exploitation of fish processing side-streams (FPS) by obtaining bio-actives and gelatine for high value-added food supplements, skin care products and biodegradable and compostable barrier layer for food packaging.

In the frames of this project, SAES Group Research laboratories are particularly involved in the development and pilot scale production of a bio-based barrier coating for flexible films.

The developed formulation is predominantly composed of fish gelatin and non-collagenic proteins; an extensive research activity was performed to identify a suitable approach, based on green additives (pH modifiers, plasticizer) and formulation parameters (mixing temperature and time), in order to stabilize the lacquer and ensure the processability for industrial deposition.

A complete characterization has been performed to assess the chemical, physical and functional properties of the material, starting from water-based lacquer, through dry coating and multilayer laminated structure.

In the next two years, SAES will be in charge of the scale up of the industrial product, dealing with the production of the lacquer up to 100L batch and the lacquering deposition on roll-to-roll pilot line.

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POST-HOUSEHOLD RECYCLED LDPE FROM USED BEVERAGE CARTON FOR CONTACT-SENSITIVE PACKAGING

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The upcoming legislation in the field of packaging products imposes new challenges on manufacturers and converters. The packaging industry will need to use a significantly higher amount of PCR materials (i.e. post-consumer-recyclates) in new packaging in the future. For example, in non-food packaging the PPWR (Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation) demands 35% of recycled content in the EU market in new packaging in the year 2030 and even 65% as of 2040. In contact-sensitive packaging e.g. for cosmetic or hygiene products 10% in 2030 and 25% in 2040 of recycled content will be mandatory. In these more critical fields of applications there are today very few raw material sources existing and almost none from mechanical recycling processes. The “CosPaTox” initiative created a very forward-looking guideline to build a foundation for the assessment of recycled plastics to be used in contact-sensitive non-food applications. Whilst chemical recycling is able deliver a “virgin-like” quality for the most demanding packaging applications such as food, the CosPaTox-guideline is an important tool for high quality mechanical recycling to fill the gap in an equally demanding packaging application that will still need to realize a minimum recycled content from post-consumer sources.

Saperatec is a pioneering company, developing delamination recycling for packaging materials to industrial maturity since 2010 and has launched an industrial recycling plant in 2024 for “PolyAl”, which is the plastic and aluminum reject of paper mills after defibering of used beverage carton. In Dessau-Roßlau (Germany) this plant offers an input capacity of over 30.000 t/year. Delamination recycling is a hot wash process treating a multilayer material with a specially formulated separation fluid. This enters the boundary layers of the different materials and separates the layers without dissolving or transforming the respective materials, to enable the mechanical recycling of PolyAl, which was formerly condemned to “energetic recycling”. All chemicals used in the process are listed in European food contact regulation without specific migration limits and are recirculated many times. Due to this unique approach Saperatec’s polyolefins are recovered at high quality to produce film-grade LDPE, which is able to meet the standards proposed by the CosPaTox guidelines. This makes the delamination recycling an extraordinary environmentally friendly process and gives access to new feedstocks for recycled products for contact-sensitive packaging.

HEAT-ASSISTED SOLUTION BLOW SPINNING FOR ACTIVE PACKAGING: ONE-STEP FABRICATION OF CROSSLINKED POLYVINYL ALCOHOL FIBERS WITH ENCAPSULATED ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS

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Introduction

Solution Blow Spinning (SBS) enables rapid polymeric fiber fabrication but is limited by the low evaporation rates of aqueous solvents. To overcome this, we developed Heat-Assisted Solution Blow Spinning (HA-SBS), which allows the one-step production of crosslinked polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) fibers from aqueous solutions [1-2]. By incorporating carvacrol (CRV) and/or graphene nanoplatelets (GNP), we created four fibrous systems for active packaging applications. HA-SBS membranes retained their structural integrity even after moisture exposure. GNP improved crosslinking and mechanical properties, while release studies confirmed sustained CRV release, ensuring prolonged antimicrobial activity. This approach demonstrates the potential of HA-SBS for developing functional packaging materials with enhanced safety and shelf-life.

Materials and methods

PVA was dissolved in distilled water at 95°C for 4 hours under continuous stirring. CRV (2 wt%) and/or GNP (1 wt%) were added to the polymer solution. Fibrous membranes were fabricated using HA-SBS, which includes a compressed air source, syringe pump, and concentric nozzle spinning setup. Fibers were collected on a heated aluminum foil collector to promote solvent evaporation and fiber formation. Processing parameters: flow rate: 45 mL/h, air pressure: 0.5 MPa, needle-to-collector distance: 20 cm, spinning time: 15 min, collector temperature: 200°C, chamber temperature: 60°C.

Result and discussion

Neat PVA fibers exhibited a unimodal diameter distribution (~1 μm) and a smooth morphology. GNP addition (PVA/GNP) led to fiber bundling and a 50% increase in fiber diameter due to viscosity enhancement. CRV addition resulted in homogeneous fibers with some beads and a 20% diameter reduction, likely due to changes in viscosity and polymer dynamics. The PVA/CRV-GNP system produced defect-free fibers without bundling, indicating a balanced interaction between CRV and GNP. Fiber bundling in PVA/GNP was attributed to solution instability, while GNP increased viscosity, counteracting CRV's viscosity-reducing effect. All samples exhibited wavy fiber morphologies, likely due to thermal stabilization during collection [1].

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360° SHELF LIFE OF STRACCHINO CHEESE:

INTEGRATING PCA AND DATA FUSION FOR MULTI-TECHNIQUE SPOILAGE ANALYSIS

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This study investigated the degradation mechanisms of stracchino cheese packaged in Modified Atmosphere Packaging (MAP) and stored both at refrigerated conditions (4°C) and thermal abuse (8°C). Microbiological, chemical, and physical analyses were conducted to monitor changes throughout the storage period. The study identified key spoilage markers, including microbial populations, volatile organic compounds (VOCs), and physical quality attributes. Microbiological assessments revealed that lactic acid bacteria and Enterobacteriaceae were the dominant microbial species in stracchino cheese, with microbial loads approaching spoilage thresholds within 10 days of storage. VOC analysis detected spoilage markers such as hexanoic acid, butanoic acid, and acetic acid, which were strongly associated with off-odor development. Physical analyses highlighted significant textural changes, including softening and moisture loss. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and data fusion techniques were used to correlate microbiological, chemical, and physical indicators, offering a holistic understanding of spoilage dynamics. This study also validated bioplastic colorimetric sensor arrays (BCSA) as a novel tool for real-time freshness monitoring, demonstrating the ability to track spoilage onset effectively. These findings highlighted the importance of integrated approaches for enhancing shelf-life predictions and informed packaging innovations, contributing to reducing food waste and improving consumer safety.

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BIO-BASED MATERIALS FOR ACTIVE FOOD PACKAGING Upcycling White Grape Pomace Extract into Chitosan-Based Films

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In the last decade, the development of bio-based active films for food packaging has gained significant attention, driven by their potential to improve product shelf-life, reduce environmental impact, and promote sustainability. In this context, chitosan, a natural polysaccharide extracted from several natural sources, has been widely studied and applied as material in active packaging systems. Its main limitation is represented by the residuals of organic acids commonly used for wet processing. The present study investigates the valorization of white grape pomace, by-product of the winemaking process, to recover bioactive extracts for incorporation into chitosan-based films obtained through a novel acid-free procedure.

Initially, the white grape pomace was subjected to conventional solid-liquid extraction using a 60% ethanol solution with a ratio of 1:8. The extraction was performed at 60 °C for 1 hour, and the resulting extract was subsequently purified using Amberlite XAD16N resin. The extract purification was performed to concentrate polyphenols while removing undesirable compounds such as sugars, amino acids, and waxes. The purified extract was then characterized before its incorporation into chitosan-based film. The extract presented a total polyphenol content of 111.8 ± 2.4 mg GAE/g determined by the Folin-Ciocalteu assay. Additionally, the bioactive characteristics of the extract were evaluated by focusing on antioxidant properties, performing DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP assays. The DPPH assay revealed an antioxidant capacity of 976 ± 37.22 $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$ extract, while the ABTS assay showed a value of 570.54 ± 0.18 mg TE/g extract. Additionally, the FRAP assay indicated a notable increase in reducing power, with the purified extract reaching 5642.11 ± 161.62 $\mu\text{mol Fe(II)/g}$ extract. Chitosan solutions were prepared by means of an initial dissolution of chitosan in aqueous organic acid, subsequent neutralization, and a resulting gel dissolution in water by introducing carbon dioxide (CO₂). The carbonation process is reversible, thus facilitating the removal of acidic residues from films and coatings [1]. Acid-free chitosan films were then prepared by successfully adding the extract with a concentration in the range between 0-10% w/w_{Chitosan}. Chitosan solutions' rheological and films' properties (water stability, barrier, and optical properties) were characterized. The shear thinning behavior of the chitosan solution showed a suitable viscosity for the coating process (viscosity in the range 10^4 - 10^3 cP for shear rate 10-100 s⁻¹). Acid-free chitosan films had superior water stability, and barrier properties (Water Vapor Permeability = 0.013 ± 0.001 g mm m⁻² d⁻¹ Pa⁻¹, Oxygen Permeability = 4.1 ± 0.4 cm³ $\mu\text{m m}^{-2}$ d⁻¹ Pa⁻¹), compared to commonly acetic acid ones. The coatings were tested on model food matrices to assess their effectiveness as active edible packaging.

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SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING SOLUTIONS FOR MEAT PRODUCTS Impact on Shelf-Life, Quality, and Safety of Salami

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The increasing demand for meat products has amplified concerns regarding spoilage, safety, and environmental impact. This study explores the potential of alternative, sustainable plastic packaging materials to preserve the quality of salami. Four packaging systems (Figure 1), including bio-based materials, were assessed for their influence on color stability, microbial growth, water activity, and lipid oxidation during a 90-day refrigerated storage period under light and dark conditions.

Figure 2 Sample groups used in this study packed in: BOPA/EVOH-PE (A), BOPP-ALOX/PP (B), Bio-PET/R-PET/Bio-PET tray with upper PET-ALOX film (C) and Bio-PET/R-PET/PET tray with upper BOPET film (D).

Key findings demonstrated that alternative single-material packaging for whole salami (Figure 1B) exhibited water vapor barrier properties which were superior than the conventional packaging system (Figure 1A). The higher barrier caused condensation issues, resulting in a darker external appearance. The water activity values for these samples remained higher over the storage period, ranging from 0.82 to 0.66, with conventional packaging generally exhibiting higher values. Internal color was minimally affected, with only slight variations in L* (lightness) and a* (redness) values. In contrast, pre-sliced salami in more sustainable packaging (Figure 1C) exhibited minimal differences in the qualitative parameters, with lower CO₂ and water activity levels. Over the 90-day monitoring period, natural product evolution was observed, with a more pronounced acceleration of effects in samples stored under light conditions, notably in terms of lipid oxidation, even if the malondialdehyde concentrations remained below the rancidity threshold value.

These results emphasize the role of sustainable packaging materials in enhancing the preservation of salami, offering a more environmentally friendly alternative to conventional methods. Future research should focus on sensory evaluation and the assessment of volatile compounds to further validate the efficacy of these packaging systems in real-world applications.

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PHYSICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF ALGINATE-BASED EDIBLE COATING

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The principal role of food packaging is to protect food products from physical, chemical, and biological influences by delaying food deterioration, retaining and prolonging the beneficial effect of processing and maintaining the quality and the safety of the food, therefore extending its shelf life [1]. Recently, there has been increased interest in new packaging strategies with environmentally friendly, biodegradable and edible materials made from renewable natural polymers that can be used as active edible coatings by incorporating antimicrobial and antioxidant compounds to improve food safety and the shelf life of food products [2]. In literature, the application of emerging technologies to the development of edible coatings for food preservation has included various nanosystems, including polymeric nanoparticles, nanoemulsions and nanocomposites, to enhance solubility, improve bioavailability, facilitate controlled release, and protect bioactive components during manufacture and storage [3]. Among several techniques adopted to protect the bioactive compounds, such as polymeric nanoparticles, nanoemulsions, and nano-systems, hydroxyapatite crystals seem to be attractive candidates for this application. Hydroxyapatite (HA) is an emerging bioceramic, which is widely used in various biomedical applications, mainly in orthopaedics and dentistry due to its close similarities with the inorganic mineral component of bone and teeth [4, 5]. HA is a calcium phosphate that possesses several properties such as biocompatibility, biomimetic dimensions and degradability, and thus it is an attractive candidate as a biomaterial with several potential applications. The composition and structure of HA nanoparticles highlighted the capability of this mineral to chemically interact with different organic molecules and thus could represent a potential carrier for the delivery of bioactive compounds in the development of edible coating systems [6]. The use of HA as a carrier in active food packaging could protect the active compound from environmental factors, processing and storage conditions, allowing the maintenance of the compound's antimicrobial and antioxidant properties to extend the shelf life of foods. HA meets the requirements of current European Community regulations for Food additives, EC 231/2012 [E341(iii)]. In this regard, our research has focused attention on the development of an edible coating activated by the addition of hydroxyapatite (HA) complexed with quercetin (QUE) as antioxidant and antimicrobial compound. A morphological characterization of hydroxyapatite-quercetin complexes was performed using Scanning Electron Microscopy, Zeta potential and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy analysis. The HA-QUE-based edible coating was prepared by the *layer-by-layer* technique, which involves the electrostatic deposition of two or more biopolymer solutions containing polyelectrolytes of opposite charge. The coatings with and without HA-QUE have been characterized by some of the common physical and technological properties of food films, such as film thickness, water holding capacity, and colour.

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BIO-BASED ANTIMICROBIAL FOOD PACKAGING COATINGS

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Antimicrobial food packaging is an innovative active packaging technology designed to enhance food quality and safety while extending the shelf life of food products. Recent advancements focus on coating traditional packaging materials with non-toxic, antimicrobial materials. Chitosan (CS), a biodegradable natural polymer recognized as Generally Recognized As Safe (GRAS), shows significant promise due to its inherent antimicrobial and film-forming properties. However, its antimicrobial action is active only under highly acidic conditions, when the amine groups become protonated and positively charged. This study presents a sustainable and scalable approach for developing stable antimicrobial coatings on commercially available food packaging materials. These coatings are based on cross-linked quaternized chitosan (QCS), which exhibits enhanced antimicrobial properties compared to native chitosan. These coatings are chemically bound to polyethylene (PE) flexible films using an FDA-approved cross-linker. Lab-scale coatings of cross-linked QCS demonstrated remarkable stability, remaining adhered to the PE surfaces even after one month of immersion in water. The mechanical and thermal properties of the coated PE films were unaffected by the processing conditions, while their oxygen and water vapor barrier properties were significantly improved, indicating that the coating functions as an additional barrier to oxygen and moisture transport. Furthermore, the QCS coatings demonstrated strong antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* strains, attributed to the cationic groups along the polymer chains, which destabilize the bacterial cell membrane. The antimicrobial packaging coating process was successfully scaled up using industrial rotogravure printing in a roll-to-roll system and was applied to package 2,000 samples of Feta cheese, a key product of the Greek dairy industry. This innovative packaging proved suitable for industrial application, preserving microbiological safety and sensory attributes over six months. Additionally, it demonstrated an extension of the shelf life of the product compared to conventional packaging. Its antimicrobial efficacy against *Listeria monocytogenes*, a significant foodborne pathogen, was assessed via inoculation trials. The results revealed strain-dependent activity, with the packaging facilitating bacterial reduction at intermediate time points, under high contamination levels. This innovative packaging offers a promising solution for enhancing food safety and quality while minimizing food waste.

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MECHANICAL RECYCLING OF POLYPROPYLENE FROM SURGICAL MASKS: VALORIZATION FOR APPLICATIONS IN CAST FILM EXTRUSION

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The COVID-19 pandemic has worsened the issue of plastic waste accumulation, leading to a surge in single-use plastics, particularly Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) used to prevent the spread of the virus. Millions of tons of additional waste, much of which ended up in landfills or oceans, underscore the urgent need for effective recycling solutions aligned with the European Green Deal and circular economy principles. In this context, this study investigates the mechanical recycling of polypropylene (PP) from disposable 3-ply surgical masks, focusing on the reprocessing of non-woven PP fabrics through extrusion while assessing the suitability of the recovered material for cast film production.

Preliminary analyses confirmed the uniform composition of the surgical mask layers, enabling their processing through single-screw extrusion without previous separation to obtain recycled polypropylene (PPr) pellets. While mechanical recycling preserved the chemical integrity of the original material, some degradation was observed, as indicated by an increased crystallization temperature and reduced viscosity. To enhance the properties of recycled PP, blends with a virgin polypropylene (PPv) graded for film extrusion were prepared in a twin-screw extruder and examined in three compositions: PPv/PPr 90/10, 70/30, and 50/50 by weight. Results demonstrated that incorporating up to 30% PPr maintained a suitable Melt Flow Rate for cast film production while optimizing thermal and rheological properties.

The prepared and characterized blends were then fed into a laboratory-scale cast film extrusion unit to produce prototype films for mechanical characterization. Films with lower PPr content (10–30%) exhibited improved transparency and fewer surface defects. In terms of mechanical properties, blends with up to 30% PPr retained stiffness and ductility comparable to 100% virgin PP films, while a 50% PPr content increased elastic modulus with only a minor reduction in elongation at break.

These findings underscore the potential of recycling strategies to transform discarded surgical masks from waste into valuable resources, recovering a vital material that remains suitable for various applications. This approach aligns with the principles of the circular economy, promoting sustainability and reducing plastic waste.

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ISSUE OF NANOCELLULOSE MIGRATION IN FOOD PACKAGING And Regulatory implications

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Nanomaterials have recently attracted great interest for their potential application as additives in food packaging. The current research in this sector also inclines towards the use of environmentally friendly alternatives to polymer-based packaging. Nanocellulose (NC), being originated from renewable resources, can play an important role in providing sustainable solutions for food packaging by providing excellent barrier and mechanical properties¹. However, safety concerns are inevitable in the case of food contact applications. According to the research on toxicity of NC so far, various forms of NC like cellulose nanofibrils (CNFs), Bacterial nanocellulose (BNC) and cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) pose no chronic toxic traits². But, there is no specific regulation governing the production and usage of nanocellulose based additives in food packaging. Commission Regulation No. EU 10/2011, which regulates all the plastic materials coming in contact with food, also misses to address the requirements and the specific migration limits for nanomaterials. In summary, most studies on nanomaterial migration have high variance and are mostly focused on metallic nanoparticles and their oxides; the data available on organic nanomaterials such as nanocellulose and nanochitin, which have a high potential in the food packaging application, are very scarce due to the lack of an efficient analytical technique capable to measure the specific migration. The objective of this discussion is to highlight these issues and analyse existing solutions with criticalities related to their use. Furthermore, the presentation will include results from morphological studies of nanocellulose-based coatings after interaction with various food simulants, as well as preliminary data on the release of volatile and non-volatile compounds from these coatings at different contact periods and conditions. These findings will contribute as an input to the development of an analytical tool to quantify specific migration of nanocellulose based additives, addressing the current gaps in regulatory frameworks and ensuring safer applications in food packaging.

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MULTIFUNCTIONAL BIO-COATINGS FOR SUSTAINABLE PAPER-BASED FOOD PACKAGING SOLUTIONS

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The transition to sustainable packaging is advancing rapidly, driven by the need to reduce environmental impact. Paper-based substrates, valued for their biodegradability and renewability, face challenges such as hydrophilicity, no sealability, and inadequate barrier properties against moisture, oxygen, and grease. Coating technology offers a cost-effective solution to enhance these properties, ensuring functionality while maintaining environmental benefits [1].

In this study, a paper-based packaging system was developed using the double-coating technique and analyzed for its chemical, thermal, and functional properties to assess its suitability for food packaging application. Kraft paper (KP) with a grammage of 100 g/m² was first coated with an ethylene-modified water-resistant polyvinyl alcohol (m-PVOH) for gas and grease barrier properties. A second layer of Mater-Bi™ (MB), enriched with 10%, 20% and 30% w/w natural carnauba wax (CW), was applied to enhance hydrophobicity and deliver sealability.

The m-PVOH layer, owing to its intrinsic barrier properties [2], provided an effective protection against O₂ with an oxygen transmission rate of 588.3 cm³/(m²·day) at 23°C and 50% RH, along with excellent grease resistance, achieving the maximum KIT value of 12. The addition of the flexible MB-based layer enhanced the mechanical properties, improving tensile strength and elongation at break. This resulted in a 26.7% increase in tensile energy absorption compared to the KP/m-PVOH sample. The incorporation of CW into the MB matrix induced microstructural changes, as observed through scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Increasing CW content resulted in a more inhomogeneous morphology and greater surface roughness due to the agglomeration of CW particles. This, combined with the hydrophobic properties of the wax [3], contributed to an increase in the water contact angle (WCA), exceeding 104° for the sample with 30% CW. Seal strength optimization via Response Surface Methodology (RSM) identified the optimal temperature, CW content, and sealing time and pressure values for achieving a balance between hydrophobicity and sealability for easy-peel food packaging applications.

This work highlights the potential of m-PVOH, MB and CW bio-coatings to create multifunctional barrier, sealable, and hydrophobic paper-based materials, offering a sustainable alternative to plastic packaging. The results provide a foundation for industrial-scale applications, supporting the development of eco-friendly solutions in the food packaging sector.

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FIBRE-BASED PACKAGING AND BARRIER COATINGS Influence on the converting and recycling

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Abstract

Currently, most of the coated cellulosic packaging on the market is extrusion-coated or laminated. Dispersion coating (DC) represents an interesting technology that is gaining interest from the industry, especially for fibre-based packaging, since it allows a lower final dry coat grammage, still ensuring remarkable barrier properties for a reduced noncellulosic content [1], [2]. Nevertheless, it is still not broadly documented how coatings perform when the coated substrate is converted, nor is the recyclability score – though previous studies [2], [3] reported that DCs can be recycled, generating low reject fractions.

In this work, different commercial and lab-developed DCs were applied on paper and paperboard. Coated substrates were subjected to converting processes, i.e., heat sealing, folding, creasing, and press-forming. For each, the effect of peculiar properties on coat integrity was monitored and compared to – in the case of paperboard – commercially laminated paperboard with PET. Finally, recyclability testing of coated paperboards was performed according to UNI 11743 and Cepi v.2 methodologies, and the results were interpreted using Aticelca 501 and 4evergreen alliance evaluation systems, respectively.

Waterborne dispersions (up to 12 g/m² dry coat grammage) heat-sealed at temperatures as low as 80–90 °C, almost 100 °C less than PET (40 g/m² dry coat grammage); nevertheless, DCs provided good seal forces (15–35% lower vs. PET-coated paperboard) and substrate delamination failure mechanism. Filler content up to 40 wt% and latex T_g can effectively modulate coating stickiness (heat-sealing) and brittleness (folding, creasing). Low T_g latexes can withstand higher creasing strokes >0.6 mm since no cracking is highlighted by the OGR test at 60 °C. Demanding converting processes like tray press-forming (>50 mm deep trays) damaged the coating due to tensile stresses; by accepting lower production yields, milder processing parameters can induce fewer defects, as spotted by ethanol-based dye.

Finally, the recycling evaluation of heat-sealable paperboard substrates provided interesting results: besides low fine and coarse rejects – coherently with previous literature – two out of three samples were not recyclable due to the extreme values for macrostickies. Such results were coherent with the inorganic filler content, which proved to reduce the stickiness of the coating.

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